

Horizon 2020
Programme

D3.2 – Cost benefit analysis (CBA) of PLF and DT innovations solutions

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1. Executive summary

This report presents the assessment of sustainability aspects on environment, society and economy, as well as welfare and data management of the solutions identified during Sm@RT. It is presented in the form of a Cost-Benefit analysis.

The information contained in this report features data gathered from a variety of stakeholders involved in the small ruminant meat and dairy industries across Europe and Israel.

The report summarises the cost benefit analyses completed for 30 tools and technology solutions identified during Work Package 2. Each analysis was carried out based on information available from sources such as the Digifarms, Innovative Farms and the Scientific and Technical Group in each country.

2. Introduction

Cost benefit analyses have been prepared for solutions identified previously to answer the needs of end-users as part of Task 2.2.

3. Methodology

A cost benefit analysis template was first designed with inputs from partners and the advisory board members, based on previous projects approaches (e.g. EuroSheep). Analyses were then allocated to each partner country, based on solutions that they proposed to answer needs highlighted in Work Package 2 (Tasks 2.1 & 2.2). Some were allocated on an individual country basis whilst some were common across more than one country (Table 1 and 2). For these, one country was the lead, assisted by the countries that had also suggested the tool or technology as a solution.

Table 1 Overview of the individual cost benefit analyses prepared by each country.

Country	Tool or Technology	Page number
Estonia	Post-dried hay technology	10
Estonia	Milk feeder for kids	14
France	Connected fences	18
France	Cameras	22
France	Water meters	26
France	Walk over weighing (WOW)	30
France	3D imaging	34
France	Aptimiz app.	38
France	Dairy parlour EID reader	42
France	Milk tank weigh scale	46
Ireland	FecPak2	50

Ireland	Flock management / data recording app.	54
Ireland	Pregnancy scanning	58
Ireland	Sheep handling conveyor	62
Israel	Water enabled weigh crate	66
Italy	DCC Delaval cell counter	70
Italy	Milk flowmeter	74
Italy	Portable NIRS (Near infra-red spectroscopy)	78
Italy	Weather station & fan cooler	82
UK	EID enabled weigh crate	86
UK	DNA parentage	90
UK	Automatic grass plate meters	94

Table 2 Overview of the common cost benefit analyses prepared by each country.

Lead country	Additional countries	Tool or Technology	Page number
Hungary	Ireland, Italy, France & UK	Autodrafter	98
Ireland	UK	EID stick readers	102
Israel	Norway	Farm management software	106
Italy	France & Hungary	EID enabled automatic feeders	110
Norway	France, Italy & Ireland	Virtual fence	114
Norway	Israel	GPS collars	118
Norway	Hungary & UK	Drone	122
UK	Italy	Feed ration planner	126

The template developed for the analyses consisted of four pages of questions and information.

The first page covered the tool or technology that the analysis was covering and additional information about the country that prepared the analysis, the production type that the tool or technology was relevant for (meat, dairy or both) and a description of the benchmark farm the analysis was based on. Benchmark farms were used to give context and a practical, more applied, example relevant for the tool or technology in question. The benchmark farm description included which country the farm was located, the production type, grazing area, species on the farm (sheep and or goats), the number of animals, the main breed types and number of staff.

The second page provided information with regards to the different expenses associated with the initial set-up costs of the tool or technology, the running costs and any additional training requirements. Next, the potential benefits of the tool or technology were presented. This was presented as a list of possible benefits relating to management, the individual animal, technical aspects and others, not associated with the first three topics. A series of statements were provided and those that were applicable to the tool or technology in question were selected.

Finally, the last page allowed further information, not covered earlier in the document, to be highlighted. There was also an overall summary section which included an ease-of-use scale, ranging from 1 (Complicated) to 10 (Simple) plus information as to whether the tool or technology was deemed value for money (for the benchmark farm in the example) and if it could be recommended to different types of farms. Additional space was provided for any other useful information or comments relating to the overall summary.

4. General results

A total of 30 different cost benefit analyses have been completed.

4.1. Initial set-up costs

Capital costs (for large items such as a weigh crate, autodrafter etc.) were associated with 25 of the 30 tools or technologies, with costs ranging from €1-500 (n=3) up to over €15,000 (n=6). The distribution of costs is given in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Number of tools or technologies falling within each capital cost category, including those where capital costs were not applicable (NA)

Individual costs (for smaller items, such as an electronic ear tag, a sample, a collar etc.) were associated with 17 of the 30 tools or technologies. Most (n=14) fell within the range of €1-20 with the remaining three in the €51-200 category (Figure 2). Many of the individual costs within the €1-20 were associated with the electronic ear tag that the animal would require to have to make full use of the tool or technology in question.

Figure 2 Number of tools or technologies falling within each individual cost category, including those where individual costs were not applicable (NA)

The suggested lifetime of each tool or technology was over 5 years. Nine of the 30 tools and technologies may involve an additional increase in the farm infrastructure whereas the remaining 21 involved no change at all.

4.2. Running costs

The power source required for each tool or technology is summarised in Figure 3. The majority required mains only (n=13) or battery (n=7). Four were allocated to the “other” group as these were mainly computer applications or software (Aptimiz software, flock management/data recording application, the farm management software & the feed ration planner). The DNA parentage sampling tool did not require any power source at all.

Figure 3. Power source requirements for the 30 tools and technologies presented

The information provided in terms of subscription fees found that 10 of the tools or technologies involved additional subscription fees, mostly charged on a per unit basis (n=6), with the remaining ones

applicable to the overall flock/herd (n=3) or the number of individual animals (n=1). The frequency and costs of the subscriptions are given in Table 3.

Table 3 Frequency and costs of subscriptions

Tool or Technology	CBA prepared by (country)	Sub. per	Sub. frequency	Sub. cost category (€)
Aptimiz software	France	Unit	Annual	201-500
Cameras	France	Unit	Monthly	1-50
Connected fences	France	Unit	Monthly	1-50
Farm management software	Israel	Flock/herd	Annual	51-200
FecPak2	Ireland	Unit	Annual	>500
Flock management / data recording app. (pedigree users)	Ireland	Flock/herd	Annual	51-200
GPS collars	Norway	Unit	Annual	1-50
Virtual fence	Norway	Unit	Annual	51-200
Water enabled weighed crate	Israel	Animal	Monthly	1-50
Water meters	France	Flock/herd	Annual	201-500

Should any maintenance help or replacement parts be required, this was deemed to be easily obtainable for 14 tools and technologies. One was difficult (EID weigh crate) and 11 were unsure. Answers were not applicable for 4 tools and technologies (Figure 4).

**Figure 4. Is maintenance help or replacement parts easy to obtain?
Answer not applicable (NA).**

4.3. Training requirements

Training was suggested for 26 of the tools and technologies. Ten were deemed to require up to an hours training whilst it was estimated that another 10 would require up to half a days training. The remaining four that did not require any training were the Camera, Connected fences, the Delaval cell counter and the Pregnancy scanning service.

Figure 5 Suggested training time range for each tool or technology

Additional technical advice (e.g. from an advisor) was recommended for 14 of the tools and technologies.

4.4. Benefits

The benefits of each tool or technology were summarised across four main topics; management, the individual animal, technical aspects and other. The number of tools or technologies associated with the different management benefits are shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6. Management associated benefits for each tool and technology

The main management benefits highlighted by the most tools and technologies were labour/time saving, better individual animal management and increased information on the production system.

The benefits selected for the remaining topics (the individual animal, technical aspects and other) are shown in Figure 7. The most commonly selected benefits were reduced stress to the animal(s), improved welfare of the animal(s), easy to use once installed and reduced stress to the farmer/staff.

Figure 7 Benefits associated with the animal, technical aspects and other, for each tool and technology

4.5. Overall summary of the tool / technology

An overall ease-of use-score was given to each tool or technology, based on a scale from 1 (complicated) to 10 (simple). The summary of the scores awarded are given in Figure 8. The majority of tools and technologies were scored 7 or above (n=25). Those at the lower end of the scale were the FecPak2 (score 4), the drone and the EID stick reader (score 5) and the milk flow meter (score 6). The water-enabled weigh crate, from Israel, was given the highest score of 10.

Figure 8 Summary of the ease-of-use scores awarded

Based on the benchmark farm information provided, 20 of the tools or technologies were deemed to be value for money, with 9 classed as maybe. The sheep handling conveyor was classed as not value for money, based on the benchmark farm in Ireland.

Twenty four of the tools and technologies were recommended for use on other types of farms, with 6 maybe recommended. There were no tools or technologies that weren't recommended for other types of farms.

5. Conclusions

The information provided in each cost benefit analyses allows potential end-users to assess whether the tool or technology is appropriate for their farming needs, system and budget. The information is provided independently and therefore should be less susceptible to any potential bias from the specific companies themselves. The impact of using each tool and technology are highlighted by the range of potential benefits associated with social, environmental and welfare topics. Benefits relating to the welfare of both the farmer and animal were evident for many of the solutions proposed. The documents will be added to the guidelines prepared for each tool or technology.

Completed cost benefit analyses are presented in the remainder of this document.

Sm@ll Ruminant Technologies

Cost/Benefit Analysis

Tool / Technology: **Post dried hay technology**

Analysis prepared by (country): **Estonia**

Production type the tool/technology is relevant for Dairy / Meat / Both

Description of the “benchmark” farm for which the analysis is performed:

Country: Estonia

Production type:

Mainly outdoors / Housed 0-3 months a year / Housed 4-8 months a year / Mainly indoors

Farm grazing area:

Species: Sheep / Goat

Number of animals: 260 milking goats

Breed: Thuringian

Number of staff: 1

Costs

Initial set-up

- **Capital costs (Large items e.g. a weigh crate, auto-drafter, etc.):**

€1 - €500 €501- €1,000 €1,001-€2,500 €2,501-€5,000 €5,001-€15,000 > €15,000

- **Individual costs (Smaller items e.g. per tag, per sample, per collar):**

€1 - €20 €21- €50 €51-€200 €201-€500 > €500

- **Equipment leasing costs (if not purchased):**

Annual Monthly Weekly €1 - €50 €51-€200 €201-€500 > €500

- **Lifetime of the technology (approximately how long will it last before needing replaced)?**

1 – 4 weeks 1-6 months 6 – 12 months 1-2 years 2-5 years > 5 years

- **Farm infrastructure requirements:** Decrease Increase No change

- **Percentage of animals within the flock/herd that use/are equipped/take advantage of the technology? 100 %**

Running costs

- **Power source requirements (tick all that apply):**

Not required Mains Battery Solar Other

- **Subscription fee – Needed? Yes / **No****

○ If yes

Per flock / herd <input type="checkbox"/>	Per individual animal <input type="checkbox"/>	Per unit <input type="checkbox"/>
Annual <input type="checkbox"/>	Monthly <input type="checkbox"/>	Weekly <input type="checkbox"/>
€1 - €50 <input type="checkbox"/>	€51 - €200 <input type="checkbox"/>	€201 - €500 <input type="checkbox"/>
		Over €500 <input type="checkbox"/>

- **Additional licences or permits required? **No** / Yes – Annual / Yes – Monthly / Yes - Weekly**

If yes, cost: €1 - €50 €51 - €200 €201 - €500 Over €500

- **Maintenance cost – included in the subscription? Yes / **No** / Not applicable**

If no, cost per month: €1 - €50 €51 - €200 €201 - €500 Over €500

- **Maintenance / replacement parts:**

Easy to obtain Difficult to obtain Not obtainable Don't know

- **Technical / mechanical support provided on farm, after purchase? **Yes** / No**

Training requirements

- **Training required to install / use? **Yes** / No**

If yes, time range? Up to an hour Half day Full day More

- **Additional technical advice required (e.g. advisor time)? **Yes** / No**

- **Are there additional costs associated with training and/or technical advice? Yes / **No****

Benefits (tick all that apply)

Management

- Labour / time saving.
- Accuracy of records (health, management, movements etc.).
- Management decisions for animal groupings.
- Better individual animal management.
- Improved medicine use.
- Better nutrition / meeting requirements better.
- Improved use of feed resource (grazing, concentrates, etc.).
- Product quality improvements (e.g. hay, carcass, growth, milk, etc.).
- Increased information on production system.
- Opportunity for sharing / moving device (more than one location).

Animal

- Reduced stress to the animal(s).
- Improved welfare of the animals(s).
- Additional information on animal behaviour.
- Information on water intake / water availability.
- Information on food intake / food availability.

Technical

- Compatibility with other devices.
- Ease of data transfer to other software.
- Easy to use once installed.

Other

- Reduced stress to farmer / staff.
- Environmental benefits (e.g. reduced wastage, improved biodiversity, etc.)
- Helps to attract new entrants into the small ruminant industries.

Another benefit not listed? Please give details:

Complete solution for the whole farm on feeding dry hay throughout the year indoor situation. High-quality hay without silage ensures high-quality production (raw milk and milk products without Clostridial bacteria). Good animal health. Pure air in a barn. Optimization of working load (1 person could feed 500 goats a day). Possibility to earn extra income with marketing high quality hay for pet rodents.

Can be used to dry other materials than grass.

Overall summary:

- **Ease of use?** *Scale 1 (Complicated) – 10 (Simple)*

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

- **Value for money (for this type of benchmark farm)?** **Yes / No / ~~Maybe~~**

- **Recommend this tool/technology for use on other types of farm?**

Yes / No / ~~Maybe~~

- **Additional comments?**

After the cut, the grass is allowed to wilt for one day (or less) on the field and is then transferred to bunkers. Drying system has various sensors for monitoring air temperature and humidity at different heights of the bunker during the post drying process. The system moves valves as needed. The system uses either warm dry air from attic room or switches on the dryer for removing excess moisture from the air. This is powered by electricity mainly sourced from solar panels. The barn has double ceiling under black tin roof. The sun heats black roof, the air is heated and directed through tunnels to the bunkers. The dried hay is delivered by a suspended forklift on overhead rails. This system ensures year-round high quality hay for the feeding of dairy goats.

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Sm@ll Ruminant Technologies

Cost/Benefit Analysis

Tool / Technology: **Automatic milk feeder for kids (GEA Farm Technology)**

Analysis prepared by (country): **Estonia**

Production type the tool/technology is relevant for: Dairy / Meat / **Both**

Description of the “benchmark” farm for which the analysis is performed:

Country: Estonia

Production type:

Mainly outdoors / Housed 0-3 months a year / Housed 4-8 months a year / **Mainly indoors**

Farm grazing area: zero grazing

Species: Sheep / **Goat**

Number of animals: 450-500 goat kids

Breed: Thuringian

Number of staff: 1

Costs

Initial set-up

- **Capital costs (Large items e.g. a weigh crate, auto-drafter, etc.):**

€1 - €500 €501- €1,000 €1,001-€2,500 €2,501-€5,000 €5,001-€15,000 > €15,000

- **Individual costs (Smaller items e.g. per tag, per sample, per collar):**

€1 - €20 €21- €50 €51-€200 €201-€500 > €500

- **Equipment leasing costs (if not purchased):**

Annual Monthly Weekly €1 - €50 €51-€200 €201-€500 > €500

- **Lifetime of the technology (approximately how long will it last before needing replaced)?**

1 – 4 weeks 1-6 months 6 – 12 months 1-2 years 2-5 years > 5 years

- **Farm infrastructure requirements:** Decrease Increase No change

- **Percentage of animals within the flock/herd that use/are equipped/take advantage of the technology? 60 %**

Running costs

- **Power source requirements (tick all that apply):**

Not required Mains Battery Solar Other

- **Subscription fee – Needed? Yes / No**

- If yes

Per flock / herd <input type="checkbox"/>	Per individual animal <input type="checkbox"/>	Per unit <input type="checkbox"/>
Annual <input type="checkbox"/>	Monthly <input type="checkbox"/>	Weekly <input type="checkbox"/>
€1 - €50 <input type="checkbox"/>	€51 - €200 <input type="checkbox"/>	€201 - €500 <input type="checkbox"/>
		Over €500 <input type="checkbox"/>

- **Additional licences or permits required? No / Yes – Annual / Yes – Monthly / Yes - Weekly**

If yes, cost: €1 - €50 €51 - €200 €201 - €500 Over €500

- **Maintenance cost – included in the subscription? Yes / No / Not applicable**

If no, cost per month: €1 - €50 €51 - €200 €201 - €500 Over €500

- **Maintenance / replacement parts:**

Easy to obtain Difficult to obtain Not obtainable Don't know

- **Technical / mechanical support provided on farm, after purchase? Yes / No**

Training requirements

- **Training required to install / use? Yes / No**

If yes, time range? Up to an hour Half day Full day More

- **Additional technical advice required (e.g. advisor time)? Yes / No**

- **Are there additional costs associated with training and/or technical advice? Yes / No**

Benefits (tick all that apply)

Management

- Labour / time saving.
- Accuracy of records (health, management, movements etc.).
- Management decisions for animal groupings.
- Better individual animal management.
- Improved medicine use.
- Better nutrition / meeting requirements better.
- Improved use of feed resource (grazing, concentrates, etc.).
- Product quality improvements (e.g. hay, carcass, growth, milk, etc.).
- Increased information on production system.
- Opportunity for sharing / moving device (more than one location).

Animal

- Reduced stress to the animal(s).
- Improved welfare of the animals(s).
- Additional information on animal behaviour.
- Information on water intake / water availability.
- Information on food intake / food availability.

Technical

- Compatibility with other devices.
- Ease of data transfer to other software.
- Easy to use once installed.

Other

- Reduced stress to farmer / staff.
- Environmental benefits (e.g. reduced wastage, improved biodiversity, etc.)
- Helps to attract new entrants into the small ruminant industries.

Another benefit not listed? Please give details:

Consistent quality of milk replacer offered and the means of access. Higher milk intakes of the kids, less scouring, less disease and mortality of the kids. Reduced aggression. Reduced labour costs and time.

Overall summary:

- **Ease of use?** *Scale 1 (Complicated) – 10 (Simple)*
1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10
- **Value for money (for this type of benchmark farm)?** Yes / ~~No~~ / ~~Maybe~~
- **Recommend this tool/technology for use on other types of farm?**
Yes / ~~No~~ / ~~Maybe~~
- **Additional comments?**
Mainly for dairy sheep and goat farms. Meat sheep farms would only be suitable for a large number of animals to achieve profitability.
A milk replacer unit that mixes goat milk powder and water and warms it to a temperature that can be determined and regulated by the farmer.

Cost/Benefit Analysis

Tool / Technology: **Connected fences**

Analysis prepared by (country): **France**

Production type the tool/technology is relevant for: Dairy / Meat / **Both**

Description of the “benchmark” farm for which the analysis is performed:

Country: France

Production type:

Mainly outdoors / Housed 0-3 months a year / **Housed 4-8 months a year** / Mainly indoors

Farm grazing area: 25 ha

Species: Sheep / **Goat**

Number of animals: 150

Breed: Alpine / Saanen

Number of staff: 2

Costs

Initial set-up

- **Capital costs (Large items e.g. a weigh crate, auto-drafter, etc.):**

€1 - €500 €501- €1,000 €1,001-€2,500 €2,501-€5,000 €5,001-€15,000 > €15,000

- **Individual costs (Smaller items e.g. per tag, per sample, per collar):**

€1 - €20 €21- €50 €51-€200 €201-€500 > €500

- **Equipment leasing costs (if not purchased):**

Annual Monthly Weekly €1 - €50 €51-€200 €201-€500 > €500

- **Lifetime of the technology (approximately how long will it last before needing replaced)?**

1 – 4 weeks 1-6 months 6– 12 months 1-2 years 2-5 years > 5 years

- **Farm infrastructure requirements:** Decrease Increase No change

- **Percentage of animals within the flock/herd that use/are equipped/take advantage of the technology? 100%**

Running costs

- **Power source requirements (tick all that apply):**

Not required Mains Battery Solar Other

- **Subscription fee – Needed? Yes / No**

- **If yes**

Per flock / herd <input type="checkbox"/>	Per individual animal <input type="checkbox"/>	Per unit <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Annual <input type="checkbox"/>	Monthly <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Weekly <input type="checkbox"/>
€1 - €50 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	€51 - €200 <input type="checkbox"/>	€201 - €500 <input type="checkbox"/>
		Over €500 <input type="checkbox"/>

- **Additional licences or permits required? No / Yes – Annual / Yes – Monthly / Yes - Weekly**

If yes, cost: €1 - €50 €51 - €200 €201 - €500 Over €500

- **Maintenance cost – included in the subscription? Yes / No Not applicable**

If no, cost per month: €1 - €50 €51 - €200 €201 - €500 Over €500

- **Maintenance / replacement parts:**

Easy to obtain Difficult to obtain Not obtainable Don't know

- **Technical / mechanical support provided on farm, after purchase? Yes No**

Training requirements

- **Training required to install / use? Yes No**

If yes, time range? Up to an hour Half day Full day More

- **Additional technical advice required (e.g. advisor time)? Yes No**

- **Are there additional costs associated with training and/or technical advice? Yes No**

Benefits (tick all that apply)

Management

- Labour / time saving.
- Accuracy of records (health, management, movements etc.).
- Management decisions for animal groupings.
- Better individual animal management.
- Improved medicine use.
- Better nutrition / meeting requirements better.
- Improved use of feed resource (grazing, concentrates, etc.).
- Product quality improvements (e.g. hay, carcass, growth, milk, etc.).
- Increased information on production system.
- Opportunity for sharing / moving device (more than one location).

Animal

- Reduced stress to the animal(s).
- Improved welfare of the animals(s).
- Additional information on animal behaviour.
- Information on water intake / water availability.
- Information on food intake / food availability.

Technical

- Compatibility with other devices.
- Ease of data transfer to other software.
- Easy to use once installed.

Other

- Reduced stress to farmer / staff.
- Environmental benefits (e.g. reduced wastage, improved biodiversity, etc.)
- Helps to attract new entrants into the small ruminant industries.

Another benefit not listed? Please give details:

Overall summary:

- **Ease of use?** *Scale 1 (Complicated) – 10 (Simple)*
1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

- **Value for money (for this type of benchmark farm)?** Yes / No / Maybe

- **Recommend this tool/technology for use on other types of farm?**
 Yes / No / Maybe

- **Additional comments?**
Need electric fences and connectivity to be used.

Sm@ll Ruminant Technologies

Cost/Benefit Analysis

Tool / Technology: **Camera**

Analysis prepared by (country): **France**

Production type the tool/technology is relevant for: Dairy ~~(Meat)~~ Both

Description of the “benchmark” farm for which the analysis is performed:

Country: France

Production type:

Mainly outdoors / ~~Housed 0-3 months a year~~ / Housed 4-8 months a year / Mainly indoors

Farm grazing area: 70 to 80 ha

Species: ~~(Sheep)~~ / Goat

Number of animals: 450

Breed: Different breeds and crosses

Number of staff: 1

Costs

Initial set-up

- **Capital costs (Large items e.g. a weigh crate, auto-drafter, etc.):**

€1 - €500 €501- €1,000 €1,001-€2,500 €2,501-€5,000 €5,001-€15,000 > €15,000

- **Individual costs (Smaller items e.g. per tag, per sample, per collar):**

€1 - €20 €21- €50 €51-€200 €201-€500 > €500

- **Equipment leasing costs (if not purchased):**

Annual Monthly Weekly €1 - €50 €51-€200 €201-€500 > €500

- **Lifetime of the technology (approximately how long will it last before needing replaced)?**

1 – 4 weeks 1-6 months 6 – 12 months 1-2 years 2-5 years > 5 years

- **Farm infrastructure requirements:** Decrease Increase No change

- **Percentage of animals within the flock/herd that use/are equipped/take advantage of the technology? 25 to 100 %**

Running costs

- **Power source requirements (tick all that apply):**

Not required Mains Battery Solar Other

- **Subscription fee – Needed?** Yes No

- **If yes**

Per flock / herd <input type="checkbox"/>	Per individual animal <input type="checkbox"/>	Per unit <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Annual <input type="checkbox"/>	Monthly <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Weekly <input type="checkbox"/>
€1 - €50 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	€51 - €200 <input type="checkbox"/>	€201 - €500 <input type="checkbox"/>
		Over €500 <input type="checkbox"/>

- **Additional licences or permits required?** No Yes – Annual / Yes – Monthly / Yes - Weekly

If yes, cost: €1 - €50 €51 - €200 €201 - €500 Over €500

- **Maintenance cost – included in the subscription?** Yes No Not applicable

If no, cost per month: €1 - €50 €51 - €200 €201 - €500 Over €500

- **Maintenance / replacement parts:**

Easy to obtain Difficult to obtain Not obtainable Don't know

- **Technical / mechanical support provided on farm, after purchase?** Yes No

Training requirements

- **Training required to install / use?** Yes No

If yes, time range? Up to an hour Half day Full day More

- **Additional technical advice required (e.g. advisor time)?** Yes No

- **Are there additional costs associated with training and/or technical advice?** Yes No

Benefits (tick all that apply)

Management

- Labour / time saving.
- Accuracy of records (health, management, movements etc.).
- Management decisions for animal groupings.
- Better individual animal management.
- Improved medicine use.
- Better nutrition / meeting requirements better.
- Improved use of feed resource (grazing, concentrates, etc.).
- Product quality improvements (e.g. hay, carcass, growth, milk, etc.).
- Increased information on production system.
- Opportunity for sharing / moving device (more than one location).

Animal

- Reduced stress to the animal(s).
- Improved welfare of the animals(s).
- Additional information on animal behaviour.
- Information on water intake / water availability.
- Information on food intake / food availability.

Technical

- Compatibility with other devices.
- Ease of data transfer to other software.
- Easy to use once installed.

Other

- Reduced stress to farmer / staff.
- Environmental benefits (e.g. reduced wastage, improved biodiversity, etc.)
- Helps to attract new entrants into the small ruminant industries.

Another benefit not listed? Please give details:

Overall summary:

- **Ease of use?** *Scale 1 (Complicated) – 10 (Simple)*
1 2 3 4 5 6 **7** 8 9 10

- **Value for money (for this type of benchmark farm)?** Yes / No / **Maybe**

- **Recommend this tool/technology for use on other types of farm?**
Yes / No / Maybe

- **Additional comments?**

Sm@ll Ruminant Technologies

Cost/Benefit Analysis

Tool / Technology: **Water meter**

Analysis prepared by (country): **France**

Production type the tool/technology is relevant for: Dairy / Meat / **Both**

Description of the “benchmark” farm for which the analysis is performed:

Country: France

Production type:

Mainly outdoors / Housed 0-3 months a year / **Housed 4-8 months a year** / Mainly indoors

Farm grazing area:

Species: **Dairy Sheep** / Goat

Number of animals: 545

Breed: Lacaune

Number of staff: 3

Costs

Initial set-up

- **Capital costs (Large items e.g. a weigh crate, auto-drafter, etc.):**

€1 - €500 €501- €1,000 €1,001-€2,500 €2,501-€5,000 €5,001-€15,000 > €15,000

- **Individual costs (Smaller items e.g. per tag, per sample, per collar):**

€1 - €20 €21- €50 €51-€200 €201-€500 > €500

- **Equipment leasing costs (if not purchased):**

Annual Monthly Weekly €1 - €50 €51-€200 €201-€500 > €500

- **Lifetime of the technology (approximately how long will it last before needing replaced)?**

1 – 4 weeks 1-6 months 6 – 12 months 1-2 years 2-5 years > 5 years

- **Farm infrastructure requirements:** Decrease Increase No change

- **Percentage of animals within the flock/herd that use/are equipped/take advantage of the technology? 100%**

Running costs

- **Power source requirements (tick all that apply):**

Not required Mains Battery Solar Other

- **Subscription fee – Needed? (Yes) No**

- If yes

Per flock / herd <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Per individual animal <input type="checkbox"/>	Per unit <input type="checkbox"/>
Annual <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Monthly <input type="checkbox"/>	Weekly <input type="checkbox"/>
€1 - €50 <input type="checkbox"/>	€51 - €200 <input type="checkbox"/>	€201 - €500 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
		Over €500 <input type="checkbox"/>

- **Additional licences or permits required? (No) Yes – Annual / Yes – Monthly / Yes - Weekly**

If yes, cost: €1 - €50 €51 - €200 €201 - €500 Over €500

- **Maintenance cost – included in the subscription? (Yes) No / Not applicable**

If no, cost per month: €1 - €50 €51 - €200 €201 - €500 Over €500

- **Maintenance / replacement parts:**

Easy to obtain Difficult to obtain Not obtainable Don't know

- **Technical / mechanical support provided on farm, after purchase? (Yes) No**

Training requirements

- **Training required to install / use? (Yes) No**

If yes, time range? Up to an hour Half day Full day More

- **Additional technical advice required (e.g. advisor time)? Yes (No)**

- **Are there additional costs associated with training and/or technical advice? Yes (No)**

Benefits (tick all that apply)

Management

- Labour / time saving.
- Accuracy of records (health, management, movements etc.).
- Management decisions for animal groupings.
- Better individual animal management.
- Improved medicine use.
- Better nutrition / meeting requirements better.
- Improved use of feed resource (grazing, concentrates, etc.).
- Product quality improvements (e.g. hay, carcass, growth, milk, etc.).
- Increased information on production system.
- Opportunity for sharing / moving device (more than one location).

Animal

- Reduced stress to the animal(s).
- Improved welfare of the animals(s).
- Additional information on animal behaviour.
- Information on water intake / water availability.
- Information on food intake / food availability.

Technical

- Compatibility with other devices.
- Ease of data transfer to other software.
- Easy to use once installed.

Other

- Reduced stress to farmer / staff.
- Environmental benefits (e.g. reduced wastage, improved biodiversity, etc.)
- Helps to attract new entrants into the small ruminant industries.

Another benefit not listed? Please give details:

Other: water leak detection

Overall summary:

- **Ease of use?** *Scale 1 (Complicated) – 10 (Simple)*
1 2 3 4 5 6 7 **8** 9 10
- **Value for money (for this type of benchmark farm)?** **Yes** / No / Maybe
- **Recommend this tool/technology for use on other types of farm?**
Yes / No / Maybe
- **Additional comments?**

The cost of a water meter and its transmitter is low but the recording and transmission device is more important upon purchase and linked to a subscription to consult and download the data online

Cost/Benefit Analysis

Tool / Technology: **Walk-over-Weighing (WoW) weigh crate**

Analysis prepared by (country): **France**

Production type the tool/technology is relevant for: Dairy / Meat / **Both**

Description of the “benchmark” farm for which the analysis is performed:

Country: France

Production type:

Mainly outdoors / Housed 0-3 months a year / Housed 4-8 months a year / Mainly indoors

Farm grazing area: 280ha

Species: **Meat Sheep** / Goat

Number of animals: 350

Breed: Romane

Number of staff: 3

Costs

Initial set-up

- **Capital costs (Large items e.g. a weigh crate, auto-drafter, etc.):**

€1 - €500 €501- €1,000 €1,001-€2,500 €2,501-€5,000 €5,001-€15,000 > €15,000

- **Individual costs (Smaller items e.g. per tag, per sample, per collar):**

€1 - €20 €21- €50 €51-€200 €201-€500 > €500

- **Equipment leasing costs (if not purchased):**

Annual Monthly Weekly €1 - €50 €51-€200 €201-€500 > €500

- **Lifetime of the technology (approximately how long will it last before needing replaced)?**

1 – 4 weeks 1-6 months 6 – 12 months 1-2 years 2-5 years >5 years

- **Farm infrastructure requirements:** Decrease Increase No change

- **Percentage of animals within the flock/herd that use/are equipped/take advantage of the technology? 100%**

Running costs

- **Power source requirements (tick all that apply):**

Not required Mains Battery Solar Other

- **Subscription fee – Needed? Yes / No**

- **If yes**

Per flock / herd <input type="checkbox"/>	Per individual animal <input type="checkbox"/>	Per unit <input type="checkbox"/>
Annual <input type="checkbox"/>	Monthly <input type="checkbox"/>	Weekly <input type="checkbox"/>
€1 - €50 <input type="checkbox"/>	€51 - €200 <input type="checkbox"/>	€201 - €500 <input type="checkbox"/>
		Over €500 <input type="checkbox"/>

- **Additional licences or permits required? No** Yes – Annual / Yes – Monthly / Yes - Weekly

If yes, cost: €1 - €50 €51 - €200 €201 - €500 Over €500

- **Maintenance cost – included in the subscription? Yes / No** **Not applicable**

If no, cost per month: €1 - €50 €51 - €200 €201 - €500 Over €500

- **Maintenance / replacement parts:**

Easy to obtain Difficult to obtain Not obtainable Don't know

- **Technical / mechanical support provided on farm, after purchase? Yes / No**

Training requirements

- **Training required to install / use? Yes** No

If yes, time range? Up to an hour Half day Full day More

- **Additional technical advice required (e.g. advisor time)? Yes / No**

- **Are there additional costs associated with training and/or technical advice? Yes / No**

Benefits (tick all that apply)

Management

- Labour / time saving.
- Accuracy of records (health, management, movements etc.).
- Management decisions for animal groupings.
- Better individual animal management.
- Improved medicine use.
- Better nutrition / meeting requirements better.
- Improved use of feed resource (grazing, concentrates, etc.).
- Product quality improvements (e.g. hay, carcass, growth, milk, etc.).
- Increased information on production system.
- Opportunity for sharing / moving device (more than one location).

Animal

- Reduced stress to the animal(s).
- Improved welfare of the animals(s).
- Additional information on animal behaviour.
- Information on water intake / water availability.
- Information on food intake / food availability.

Technical

- Compatibility with other devices.
- Ease of data transfer to other software.
- Easy to use once installed.

Other

- Reduced stress to farmer / staff.
- Environmental benefits (e.g. reduced wastage, improved biodiversity, etc.)
- Helps to attract new entrants into the small ruminant industries.

Another benefit not listed? Please give details:

Overall summary:

- **Ease of use?** *Scale 1 (Complicated) – 10 (Simple)*
1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

- **Value for money (for this type of benchmark farm)?** Yes / No / Maybe

- **Recommend this tool/technology for use on other types of farm?**
 Yes / No / Maybe

- **Additional comments?**

Possible recommendation for making ingested quantities. As well as possible recommendation for goats and milking sheep. You just need to make the right choice of location for the device.

Cost/Benefit Analysis

Tool / Technology: **3D imaging**

Analysis prepared by (country): **France**

Production type the tool/technology is relevant for: Dairy / Meat / **Both**

Description of the “benchmark” farm for which the analysis is performed:

Country: France

Production type:

Mainly outdoors / Housed 0-3 months a year / **Housed 4-8 months a year** / Mainly indoors

Farm grazing area: 25 ha

Species: Sheep / **Goat**

Number of animals: 150

Breed: Alpine / Saanen

Number of staff: 2

Costs

Initial set-up

- **Capital costs (Large items e.g. a weigh crate, auto-drafter, etc.):**

€1 - €500 €501- €1,000 €1,001-€2,500 €2,501-€5,000 €5,001-€15,000 > €15,000

- **Individual costs (Smaller items e.g. per tag, per sample, per collar):**

€1 - €20 €21- €50 €51-€200 €201-€500 > €500

- **Equipment leasing costs (if not purchased):**

Annual Monthly Weekly €1 - €50 €51-€200 €201-€500 > €500

- **Lifetime of the technology (approximately how long will it last before needing replaced)?**

1 – 4 weeks 1-6 months 6 – 12 months 1-2 years 2-5 years >5 years

- **Farm infrastructure requirements:** Decrease Increase No change

- **Percentage of animals within the flock/herd that use/are equipped/take advantage of the technology? 100%**

Running costs

- **Power source requirements (tick all that apply):**

Not required Mains Battery Solar Other

- **Subscription fee – Needed? Yes / No** (No circled)

- If yes

Per flock / herd <input type="checkbox"/>	Per individual animal <input type="checkbox"/>	Per unit <input type="checkbox"/>
Annual <input type="checkbox"/>	Monthly <input type="checkbox"/>	Weekly <input type="checkbox"/>
€1 - €50 <input type="checkbox"/>	€51 - €200 <input type="checkbox"/>	€201 - €500 <input type="checkbox"/> Over €500 <input type="checkbox"/>

- **Additional licences or permits required? No / Yes – Annual / Yes – Monthly / Yes - Weekly** (No circled)

If yes, cost: €1 - €50 €51 - €200 €201 - €500 Over €500

- **Maintenance cost – included in the subscription? Yes / No / Not applicable** (Not applicable circled)

If no, cost per month: €1 - €50 €51 - €200 €201 - €500 Over €500

- **Maintenance / replacement parts:**

Easy to obtain Difficult to obtain Not obtainable Don't know

- **Technical / mechanical support provided on farm, after purchase? Yes / No** (No circled)

Training requirements

- **Training required to install / use? Yes / No** (Yes circled)

If yes, time range? Up to an hour Half day Full day More

- **Additional technical advice required (e.g. advisor time)? Yes / No** (No circled)

- **Are there additional costs associated with training and/or technical advice? Yes / No** (No circled)

Benefits (tick all that apply)

Management

- Labour / time saving.
- Accuracy of records (health, management, movements etc.).
- Management decisions for animal groupings.
- Better individual animal management.
- Improved medicine use.
- Better nutrition / meeting requirements better.
- Improved use of feed resource (grazing, concentrates, etc.).
- Product quality improvements (e.g. hay, carcass, growth, milk, etc.).
- Increased information on production system.
- Opportunity for sharing / moving device (more than one location).

Animal

- Reduced stress to the animal(s).
- Improved welfare of the animals(s).
- Additional information on animal behaviour.
- Information on water intake / water availability.
- Information on food intake / food availability.

Technical

- Compatibility with other devices.
- Ease of data transfer to other software.
- Easy to use once installed.

Other

- Reduced stress to farmer / staff.
- Environmental benefits (e.g. reduced wastage, improved biodiversity, etc.)
- Helps to attract new entrants into the small ruminant industries.

Another benefit not listed? Please give details:

Overall summary:

- **Ease of use?** *Scale 1 (Complicated) – 10 (Simple)*
1 2 3 4 5 6 **7** 8 9 10

- **Value for money (for this type of benchmark farm)?** Yes / No / **Maybe**

- **Recommend this tool/technology for use on other types of farm?**
Yes / No / Maybe

- **Additional comments?**
3D Imaging tool is still a prototype so not commercially available yet.

Cost/Benefit Analysis

Tool / Technology: **Aptimiz software**

Analysis prepared by (country): **France**

Production type the tool/technology is relevant for: Dairy / Meat / **Both**

Description of the “benchmark” farm for which the analysis is performed:

Country: France

Production type:

Mainly outdoors / Housed 0-3 months a year / **Housed 4-8 months a year** / Mainly indoors

Farm grazing area: 40 ha

Species: Sheep / **Goat**

Number of animals: 220

Breed: Alpine/Saanens

Number of staff: 2

Costs

Initial set-up

- **Capital costs (Large items e.g. a weigh crate, auto-drafter, etc.):**

€1 - €500 €501- €1,000 €1,001-€2,500 €2,501-€5,000 €5,001-€15,000 > €15,000

- **Individual costs (Smaller items e.g. per tag, per sample, per collar):**

€1 - €20 €21- €50 €51-€200 €201-€500 > €500

- **Equipment leasing costs (if not purchased):**

Annual Monthly Weekly €1 - €50 €51-€200 €201-€500 > €500

- **Lifetime of the technology (approximately how long will it last before needing replaced)?**

1 – 4 weeks 1-6 months 6 – 12 months 1-2 years 2-5 years > 5 years

- **Farm infrastructure requirements:** Decrease Increase No change

- **Percentage of animals within the flock/herd that use/are equipped/take advantage of the technology? 0% → It is for farm staff**

Running costs

- **Power source requirements (tick all that apply):**

Not required Mains Battery Solar Other

- **Subscription fee – Needed? Yes / No**

○ If yes

Per flock / herd <input type="checkbox"/>	Per individual animal <input type="checkbox"/>	Per unit <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Annual <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Monthly <input type="checkbox"/>	Weekly <input type="checkbox"/>
€1 - €50 <input type="checkbox"/>	€51 - €200 <input type="checkbox"/>	€201 - €500 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
		Over €500 <input type="checkbox"/>

- **Additional licences or permits required? No / Yes – Annual / Yes – Monthly / Yes - Weekly**

If yes, cost: €1 - €50 €51 - €200 €201 - €500 Over €500

- **Maintenance cost – included in the subscription? Yes / No / Not applicable**

If no, cost per month: €1 - €50 €51 - €200 €201 - €500 Over €500

- **Maintenance / replacement parts:**

Easy to obtain Difficult to obtain Not obtainable Don't know

- **Technical / mechanical support provided on farm, after purchase? Yes / No**

Training requirements

- **Training required to install / use? Yes / No**

If yes, time range? Up to an hour Half day Full day More

- **Additional technical advice required (e.g. advisor time)? Yes / No**

- **Are there additional costs associated with training and/or technical advice? Yes / No**

Benefits (tick all that apply)

Management

- Labour / time saving.
- Accuracy of records (health, management, movements etc.).
- Management decisions for animal groupings.
- Better individual animal management.
- Improved medicine use.
- Better nutrition / meeting requirements better.
- Improved use of feed resource (grazing, concentrates, etc.).
- Product quality improvements (e.g. hay, carcass, growth, milk, etc.).
- Increased information on production system.
- Opportunity for sharing / moving device (more than one location).

Animal

- Reduced stress to the animal(s).
- Improved welfare of the animals(s).
- Additional information on animal behaviour.
- Information on water intake / water availability.
- Information on food intake / food availability.

Technical

- Compatibility with other devices.
- Ease of data transfer to other software.
- Easy to use once installed.

Other

- Reduced stress to farmer / staff.
- Environmental benefits (e.g. reduced wastage, improved biodiversity, etc.)
- Helps to attract new entrants into the small ruminant industries.

Another benefit not listed? Please give details:

Allows you to optimize working time.

Reduce hard work.

Overall summary:

- **Ease of use?** *Scale 1 (Complicated) – 10 (Simple)*

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

- **Value for money (for this type of benchmark farm)?** Yes / No / Maybe

- **Recommend this tool/technology for use on other types of farm?**

Yes / No / Maybe

- **Additional comments?**

Requires an advisor to use working time data and optimize time

Sm@ll Ruminant Technologies

Cost/Benefit Analysis

Tool / Technology: Dairy parlour EID reader

Analysis prepared by (country): France

Production type the tool/technology is relevant for: Dairy / Meat / Both

Description of the “benchmark” farm for which the analysis is performed:

Country: France

Production type:

Mainly outdoors / Housed 0-3 months a year / Housed 4-8 months a year / Mainly indoors

Farm grazing area: 20 ha

Species: Sheep / Goat

Number of animals: 200

Breed: Alpine / Saanen

Number of staff: 2

Costs

Initial set-up

- **Capital costs (Large items e.g. a weigh crate, auto-drafter, etc.):**

€1 - €500 €501- €1,000 €1,001-€2,500 €2,501-€5,000 €5,001-€15,000 > €15,000

- **Individual costs (Smaller items e.g. per tag, per sample, per collar):**

€1 - €20 €21- €50 €51-€200 €201-€500 > €500

- **Equipment leasing costs (if not purchased):**

Annual Monthly Weekly €1 - €50 €51-€200 €201-€500 > €500

- **Lifetime of the technology (approximately how long will it last before needing replaced)?**

1 – 4 weeks 1-6 months 6 – 12 months 1-2 years 2-5 years > 5 years

- **Farm infrastructure requirements:** Decrease Increase No change

- **Percentage of animals within the flock/herd that use/are equipped/take advantage of the technology? 100%**

Running costs

- **Power source requirements (tick all that apply):**

Not required Mains Battery Solar Other

- **Subscription fee – Needed? Yes / No**

- **If yes**

Per flock / herd <input type="checkbox"/>	Per individual animal <input type="checkbox"/>	Per unit <input type="checkbox"/>
Annual <input type="checkbox"/>	Monthly <input type="checkbox"/>	Weekly <input type="checkbox"/>
€1 - €50 <input type="checkbox"/>	€51 - €200 <input type="checkbox"/>	€201 - €500 <input type="checkbox"/>
		Over €500 <input type="checkbox"/>

- **Additional licences or permits required? No / Yes – Annual / Yes – Monthly / Yes - Weekly**

If yes, cost: €1 - €50 €51 - €200 €201 - €500 Over €500

- **Maintenance cost – included in the subscription? Yes / No / Not applicable**

If no, cost per month: €1 - €50 €51 - €200 €201 - €500 Over €500

- **Maintenance / replacement parts:**

Easy to obtain Difficult to obtain Not obtainable Don't know

- **Technical / mechanical support provided on farm, after purchase? Yes / No**

Training requirements

- **Training required to install / use? Yes / No**

If yes, time range? Up to an hour Half day Full day More

- **Additional technical advice required (e.g. advisor time)? Yes / No**

- **Are there additional costs associated with training and/or technical advice? Yes / No**

Benefits (tick all that apply)

Management

- Labour / time saving.
- Accuracy of records (health, management, movements etc.).
- Management decisions for animal groupings.
- Better individual animal management.
- Improved medicine use.
- Better nutrition / meeting requirements better.
- Improved use of feed resource (grazing, concentrates, etc.).
- Product quality improvements (e.g. hay, carcass, growth, milk, etc.).
- Increased information on production system.
- Opportunity for sharing / moving device (more than one location).

Animal

- Reduced stress to the animal(s).
- Improved welfare of the animals(s).
- Additional information on animal behaviour.
- Information on water intake / water availability.
- Information on food intake / food availability.

Technical

- Compatibility with other devices.
- Ease of data transfer to other software.
- Easy to use once installed.

Other

- Reduced stress to farmer / staff.
- Environmental benefits (e.g. reduced wastage, improved biodiversity, etc.)
- Helps to attract new entrants into the small ruminant industries.

Another benefit not listed? Please give details:

Overall summary:

- **Ease of use?** *Scale 1 (Complicated) – 10 (Simple)*
1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

- **Value for money (for this type of benchmark farm)?** Yes / No / Maybe

- **Recommend this tool/technology for use on other types of farm?**
 Yes / No / Maybe

- **Additional comments?**
ID in link with the automatic feeder in milking parlour

Horizon 2020
Programme

Cost/Benefit Analysis

Tool / Technology: **Connected milk tank weigh scales**

Analysis prepared by (country): **France**

Production type the tool/technology is relevant for **Dairy** / Meat / Both

Description of the “benchmark” farm for which the analysis is performed:

Country: France

Production type:

Mainly outdoors / Housed 0-3 months a year / **Housed 4-8 months a year** / Mainly indoors

Farm grazing area:

Species: **Dairy Sheep** / Goat

Number of animals: 545

Breed: Lacaune

Number of staff: 3

Costs

Initial set-up

- **Capital costs (Large items e.g. a weigh crate, auto-drafter, etc.):**

€1 - €500 €501- €1,000 €1,001-€2,500 €2,501-€5,000 €5,001-€15,000 > €15,000

- **Individual costs (Smaller items e.g. per tag, per sample, per collar):**

€1 - €20 €21- €50 €51-€200 €201-€500 > €500

- **Equipment leasing costs (if not purchased):**

Annual Monthly Weekly €1 - €50 €51-€200 €201-€500 > €500

- **Lifetime of the technology (approximately how long will it last before needing replaced)?**

1 – 4 weeks 1-6 months 6 – 12 months 1-2 years 2-5 years > 5 years

- **Farm infrastructure requirements:** Decrease Increase No change

- **Percentage of animals within the flock/herd that use/are equipped/take advantage of the technology? _100%**

Running costs

- **Power source requirements (tick all that apply):**

Not required Mains Battery Solar Other

- **Subscription fee – Needed? Yes / No**

○ If yes

Per flock / herd <input type="checkbox"/>	Per individual animal <input type="checkbox"/>	Per unit <input type="checkbox"/>
Annual <input type="checkbox"/>	Monthly <input type="checkbox"/>	Weekly <input type="checkbox"/>
€1 - €50 <input type="checkbox"/>	€51 - €200 <input type="checkbox"/>	€201 - €500 <input type="checkbox"/> Over €500 <input type="checkbox"/>

- **Additional licences or permits required? No / Yes – Annual / Yes – Monthly / Yes - Weekly**

If yes, cost: €1 - €50 €51 - €200 €201 - €500 Over €500

- **Maintenance cost – included in the subscription? Yes / No / Not applicable**

If no, cost per month: €1 - €50 €51 - €200 €201 - €500 Over €500

- **Maintenance / replacement parts:**

Easy to obtain Difficult to obtain Not obtainable Don't know

- **Technical / mechanical support provided on farm, after purchase? Yes / No**

Training requirements

- **Training required to install / use? Yes / No**

If yes, time range? Up to an hour Half day Full day More

- **Additional technical advice required (e.g. advisor time)? Yes / No**

- **Are there additional costs associated with training and/or technical advice? Yes / No**

Benefits (tick all that apply)

Management

- Labour / time saving.
- Accuracy of records (health, management, movements etc.).
- Management decisions for animal groupings.
- Better individual animal management.
- Improved medicine use.
- Better nutrition / meeting requirements better.
- Improved use of feed resource (grazing, concentrates, etc.).
- Product quality improvements (e.g. hay, carcass, growth, milk, etc.).
- Increased information on production system.
- Opportunity for sharing / moving device (more than one location).

Animal

- Reduced stress to the animal(s).
- Improved welfare of the animals(s).
- Additional information on animal behaviour.
- Information on water intake / water availability.
- Information on food intake / food availability.

Technical

- Compatibility with other devices.
- Ease of data transfer to other software.
- Easy to use once installed.

Other

- Reduced stress to farmer / staff.
- Environmental benefits (e.g. reduced wastage, improved biodiversity, etc.)
- Helps to attract new entrants into the small ruminant industries.

Another benefit not listed? Please give details:

Animals: Additional information on batch and herd production compared to milk control data

Management: Precise assessment of working time (linked to milking in this case)

Overall summary:

- **Ease of use?** *Scale 1 (Complicated) – 10 (Simple)*

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 **9** 10

- **Value for money (for this type of benchmark farm)?** Yes / No / **Maybe**

- **Recommend this tool/technology for use on other types of farm?**

Yes / No / Maybe

- **Additional comments?**

Farmer advantage: automatic recording of weights without manual or visual reading, possible monitoring of production if the flock size is stable.

An alert system would be really interesting, particularly for a sudden and significant drop in production.

Horizon 2020
Programme

Cost/Benefit Analysis

Tool / Technology: **FECPAKG2**

Analysis prepared by (country): **Ireland**

Production type the tool/technology is relevant for: Both

Description of the “benchmark” farm for which the analysis is performed:

Country: *Ireland*

Production type:

Housed 0-3 months a year – Meat sheep

Farm grazing area: *35ha*

Species: *Sheep*

Number of animals: *300 ewes plus their lambs and replacements*

Breed: *Suffolk x Belclare*

Number of staff: *1 farmer*

Costs

Initial set-up

- **Capital costs (Large items e.g. a weigh crate, auto-drafter, etc.):**

€1 - €500 €501- €1,000 €1,001-€2,500 €2,501-€5,000 €5,001-€15,000 > €15,000

- **Individual costs (Smaller items e.g. per tag, per sample, per collar):**

€1 - €20 €21- €50 €51-€200 €201-€500 > €500

- **Equipment leasing costs (if not purchased):**

Annual Monthly Weekly €1 - €50 €51-€200 €201-€500 > €500

- **Lifetime of the technology (approximately how long will it last before needing replaced)?**

1 – 4 weeks 1-6 months 6 – 12 months 1-2 years 2-5 years > 5 years

- **Farm infrastructure requirements:** Decrease Increase No change

- **Percentage of animals within the flock/herd that use/are equipped/take advantage of the technology? 100%, potentially all animals**

Running costs

- **Power source requirements (tick all that apply):**

Not required Mains Battery Solar Other

- **Subscription fee – Needed?** Yes

Per flock / herd <input type="checkbox"/>	Per individual animal <input type="checkbox"/>	Per unit <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Annual <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Monthly <input type="checkbox"/>	Weekly <input type="checkbox"/>
€1 - €50 <input type="checkbox"/>	€51 - €200 <input type="checkbox"/>	€201 - €500 <input type="checkbox"/>
		Over €500 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

- **Additional licences or permits required?** No

If yes, cost: €1 - €50 €51 - €200 €201 - €500 Over €500

- **Maintenance cost – included in the subscription?** Not applicable

If no, cost per month: €1 - €50 €51 - €200 €201 - €500 Over €500

- **Maintenance / replacement parts:**

Easy to obtain Difficult to obtain Not obtainable Don't know

- **Technical / mechanical support provided on farm, after purchase?** Yes

Training requirements

- **Training required to install / use?** Yes

If yes, time range? Up to an hour Half day Full day More

- **Additional technical advice required (e.g. advisor time)?** Yes

- **Are there additional costs associated with training and/or technical advice?** No

Benefits (tick all that apply)

Management

- Labour / time saving.
- Accuracy of records (health, management, movements etc.).
- Management decisions for animal groupings.
- Better individual animal management.
- Improved medicine use.
- Better nutrition / meeting requirements better.
- Improved use of feed resource (grazing, concentrates, etc.).
- Product quality improvements (e.g. hay, carcass, growth, milk, etc.).
- Increased information on production system.
- Opportunity for sharing / moving device (more than one location).

Animal

- Reduced stress to the animal(s).
- Improved welfare of the animals(s).
- Additional information on animal behaviour.
- Information on water intake / water availability.
- Information on food intake / food availability.

Technical

- Compatibility with other devices.
- Ease of data transfer to other software.
- Easy to use once installed.

Other

- Reduced stress to farmer / staff .
- Environmental benefits (e.g. reduced wastage, improved biodiversity, etc.)
- Helps to attract new entrants in to the small ruminant industries.

Another benefit not listed? Please give details:

Can help to reduce anthelmintic use and anthelmintic resistance

Overall summary:

- **Ease of use?** *Scale 1 (Complicated) – 10 (Simple)*

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

- **Value for money (for this type of benchmark farm)?** Maybe

- **Recommend this tool/technology for use on other types of farm?**

Yes but scale is required or could be shared between a group of farmers

- **Additional comments?**

Might be more suited to share between a group of farmers or a veterinary practise than for an individual farm/farmer.

Example costs - €680 per year for 200 FEC samples.

Horizon 2020
Programme

Cost/Benefit Analysis

Tool / Technology: **Flock data recording app (Sheep Ireland)**

Analysis prepared by (country): **Ireland**

Production type the tool/technology is relevant for: **Meat**

Description of the “benchmark” farm for which the analysis is performed:

Country: *Ireland*

Production type:

Housed 0-3 months a year – Meat sheep

Farm grazing area: *35 ha*

Species: *Sheep*

Number of animals: *300 ewes plus their lambs and replacements*

Breed: *Suffolk x Belclare*

Number of staff: *1 farmer*

Costs

Initial set-up

- **Capital costs (Large items e.g. a weigh crate, auto-drafter, etc.):**

€1 - €500 €501- €1,000 €1,001-€2,500 €2,501-€5,000 €5,001-€15,000 > €15,000

- **Individual costs (Smaller items e.g. per tag, per sample, per collar):**

€1 - €20 €21- €50 €51-€200 €201-€500 > €500

- **Equipment leasing costs (if not purchased):**

Annual Monthly Weekly €1 - €50 €51-€200 €201-€500 > €500

- **Lifetime of the technology (approximately how long will it last before needing replaced)?**

1 – 4 weeks 1-6 months 6 – 12 months 1-2 years 2-5 years > 5 years

- **Farm infrastructure requirements:** Decrease Increase No change

- **Percentage of animals within the flock/herd that use/are equipped/take advantage of the technology? 100% if EID tagged**

Running costs

- **Power source requirements (tick all that apply):**

Not required Mains Battery Solar Other

- **Subscription fee – Needed? Yes & No (See later comments)**

- **If yes**

Per flock / herd <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Per individual animal <input type="checkbox"/>	Per unit <input type="checkbox"/>
Annual <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Monthly <input type="checkbox"/>	Weekly <input type="checkbox"/>
€1 - €50 <input type="checkbox"/>	€51 - €200 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	€201 - €500 <input type="checkbox"/>
		Over €500 <input type="checkbox"/>

- **Additional licences or permits required? No**

If yes, cost: €1 - €50 €51 - €200 €201 - €500 Over €500

- **Maintenance cost – included in the subscription? Not applicable**

If no, cost per month: €1 - €50 €51 - €200 €201 - €500 Over €500

- **Maintenance / replacement parts:**

Easy to obtain Difficult to obtain Not obtainable Don't know

- **Technical / mechanical support provided on farm, after purchase? Yes**

Training requirements

- **Training required to install / use? Yes**

If yes, time range? Up to an hour Half day Full day More

- **Additional technical advice required (e.g. advisor time)? Yes**

- **Are there additional costs associated with training and/or technical advice? No**

Benefits (tick all that apply)

Management

- Labour / time saving.
- Accuracy of records (health, management, movements etc.).
- Management decisions for animal groupings.
- Better individual animal management.
- Improved medicine use.
- Better nutrition / meeting requirements better.
- Improved use of feed resource (grazing, concentrates, etc.).
- Product quality improvements (e.g. hay, carcass, growth, milk, etc.).
- Increased information on production system.
- Opportunity for sharing / moving device (more than one location).

Animal

- Reduced stress to the animal(s).
- Improved welfare of the animals(s).
- Additional information on animal behaviour.
- Information on water intake / water availability.
- Information on food intake / food availability.

Technical

- Compatibility with other devices.
- Ease of data transfer to other software.
- Easy to use once installed.

Other

- Reduced stress to farmer / staff.
- Environmental benefits (e.g. reduced wastage, improved biodiversity, etc.)
- Helps to attract new entrants into the small ruminant industries.

Another benefit not listed? Please give details:

Overall summary:

- **Ease of use?** *Scale 1 (Complicated) – 10 (Simple)*
1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

- **Value for money (for this type of benchmark farm)?** Yes

- **Recommend this tool/technology for use on other types of farm?**
Yes

- **Additional comments?**
Sheep Ireland membership is free for commercial farms and between €50-100/year for pedigree registered flocks.
Need a smartphone with internet access to record or upload information, or the app can be used offline and data uploaded later. Customer support provided via email and on the phone. Only available to Irish farmers.

Horizon 2020
Programme

Sm@ll Ruminant Technologies

Cost/Benefit Analysis

Tool / Technology: **Pregnancy scanning service**

Analysis prepared by (country): **Ireland**

Production type the tool/technology is relevant for: Both

Description of the “benchmark” farm for which the analysis is performed:

Country: *Ireland*

Production type:

Housed 0-3 months a year – Meat sheep

Farm grazing area: *35ha*

Species: *Sheep*

Number of animals: *300 ewes plus their lambs and replacements*

Breed: *Suffolk x Belclare*

Number of staff: *1 farmer*

Costs

Initial set-up

- **Capital costs (Large items e.g. a weigh crate, auto-drafter, etc.):**

€1 - €500 €501- €1,000 €1,001-€2,500 €2,501-€5,000 €5,001-€15,000 > €15,000

- **Individual costs (Smaller items e.g. per tag, per sample, per collar):**

€1 - €20 €21- €50 €51-€200 €201-€500 > €500

- **Equipment leasing costs (if not purchased):**

Annual Monthly Weekly €1 - €50 €51-€200 €201-€500 > €500

- **Lifetime of the technology (approximately how long will it last before needing replaced)?**

1 – 4 weeks 1-6 months 6 – 12 months 1-2 years 2-5 years > 5 years

- **Farm infrastructure requirements:** Decrease Increase No change

- **Percentage of animals within the flock/herd that use/are equipped/take advantage of the technology? All ewes and replacements**

Running costs

- **Power source requirements (tick all that apply):**

Not required Mains Battery Solar Other

- **Subscription fee – Needed?** No

- **If yes**

Per flock / herd <input type="checkbox"/>	Per individual animal <input type="checkbox"/>	Per unit <input type="checkbox"/>
Annual <input type="checkbox"/>	Monthly <input type="checkbox"/>	Weekly <input type="checkbox"/>
€1 - €50 <input type="checkbox"/>	€51 - €200 <input type="checkbox"/>	€201 - €500 <input type="checkbox"/>
		Over €500 <input type="checkbox"/>

- **Additional licences or permits required?** No

If yes, cost: €1 - €50 €51 - €200 €201 - €500 Over €500

- **Maintenance cost – included in the subscription?** Not applicable

If no, cost per month: €1 - €50 €51 - €200 €201 - €500 Over €500

- **Maintenance / replacement parts:**

Easy to obtain Difficult to obtain Not obtainable Don't know

- **Technical / mechanical support provided on farm, after purchase?** NA

Training requirements

- **Training required to install / use?** No, not for the farmer

If yes, time range? Up to an hour Half day Full day More

- **Additional technical advice required (e.g. advisor time)?** No

- **Are there additional costs associated with training and/or technical advice?** No

Benefits (tick all that apply)

Management

- Labour / time saving.
- Accuracy of records (health, management, movements etc.).
- Management decisions for animal groupings.
- Better individual animal management.
- Improved medicine use.
- Better nutrition / meeting requirements better.
- Improved use of feed resource (grazing, concentrates, etc.).
- Product quality improvements (e.g. hay, carcass, growth, milk, etc.).
- Increased information on production system.
- Opportunity for sharing / moving device (more than one location).

Animal

- Reduced stress to the animal(s).
- Improved welfare of the animals(s).
- Additional information on animal behaviour.
- Information on water intake / water availability.
- Information on food intake / food availability.

Technical

- Compatibility with other devices.
- Ease of data transfer to other software.
- Easy to use once installed.

Other

- Reduced stress to farmer / staff
- Environmental benefits (e.g. reduced wastage, improved biodiversity, etc.)
- Helps to attract new entrants into the small ruminant industries.

Another benefit not listed? Please give details:

A contractor completes the scanning so no investment needed by the farmer.

Can be used with performance recording application/software to build data set of individual and flock performance.

Overall summary:

- **Ease of use?** *Scale 1 (Complicated) – 10 (Simple)*
1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 **9** 10
- **Value for money (for this type of benchmark farm)?** Yes
- **Recommend this tool/technology for use on other types of farm?**
Yes
- **Additional comments?**

Horizon 2020
Programme

Sm@ll Ruminant Technologies

Cost/Benefit Analysis

Tool / Technology: **Sheep handling conveyer**

Analysis prepared by (country): **Ireland**

Production type the tool/technology is relevant for: Both

Description of the “benchmark” farm for which the analysis is performed:

Country: *Ireland*

Production type:

Housed 0-3 months a year – Meat sheep

Farm grazing area: *35ha*

Species: *Sheep*

Number of animals: *300 ewes plus their lambs and replacements*

Breed: *Suffolk x Belclare*

Number of staff: *1 farmer*

Costs

Initial set-up

- **Capital costs (Large items e.g. a weigh crate, auto-drafter, etc.):**

€1 - €500 €501- €1,000 €1,001-€2,500 €2,501-€5,000 €5,001-€15,000 > €15,000

- **Individual costs (Smaller items e.g. per tag, per sample, per collar):**

€1 - €20 €21- €50 €51-€200 €201-€500 > €500

- **Equipment leasing costs (if not purchased):**

Annual Monthly Weekly €1 - €50 €51-€200 €201-€500 > €500

- **Lifetime of the technology (approximately how long will it last before needing replaced)?**

1 – 4 weeks 1-6 months 6 – 12 months 1-2 years 2-5 years > 5 years

- **Farm infrastructure requirements:** Decrease Increase No change

- **Percentage of animals within the flock/herd that use/are equipped/take advantage of the technology? Up to 100%**

Running costs

- **Power source requirements (tick all that apply):**

Not required Mains Battery Solar Other

- **Subscription fee – Needed?** No

- **If yes**

Per flock / herd <input type="checkbox"/>	Per individual animal <input type="checkbox"/>	Per unit <input type="checkbox"/>
Annual <input type="checkbox"/>	Monthly <input type="checkbox"/>	Weekly <input type="checkbox"/>
€1 - €50 <input type="checkbox"/>	€51 - €200 <input type="checkbox"/>	€201 - €500 <input type="checkbox"/>
		Over €500 <input type="checkbox"/>

- **Additional licences or permits required?** No

If yes, cost: €1 - €50 €51 - €200 €201 - €500 Over €500

- **Maintenance cost – included in the subscription?** Not applicable

If no, cost per month: €1 - €50 €51 - €200 €201 - €500 Over €500

- **Maintenance / replacement parts:**

Easy to obtain Difficult to obtain Not obtainable Don't know

- **Technical / mechanical support provided on farm, after purchase?** No

Training requirements

- **Training required to install / use?** Yes

If yes, time range? Up to an hour Half day Full day More

- **Additional technical advice required (e.g. advisor time)?** No

- **Are there additional costs associated with training and/or technical advice?** No

Benefits (tick all that apply)

Management

- Labour / time saving.
- Accuracy of records (health, management, movements etc.).
- Management decisions for animal groupings.
- Better individual animal management.
- Improved medicine use.
- Better nutrition / meeting requirements better.
- Improved use of feed resource (grazing, concentrates, etc.).
- Product quality improvements (e.g. hay, carcass, growth, milk, etc.).
- Increased information on production system.
- Opportunity for sharing / moving device (more than one location).

Animal

- Reduced stress to the animal(s).
- Improved welfare of the animals(s).
- Additional information on animal behaviour.
- Information on water intake / water availability.
- Information on food intake / food availability.

Technical

- Compatibility with other devices.
- Ease of data transfer to other software.
- Easy to use once installed.

Other

- Reduced stress to farmer / staff.
- Environmental benefits (e.g. reduced wastage, improved biodiversity, etc.)
- Helps to attract new entrants into the small ruminant industries.

Another benefit not listed? Please give details:

Overall summary:

- **Ease of use?** *Scale 1 (Complicated) – 10 (Simple)*
1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

- **Value for money (for this type of benchmark farm)?** No

- **Recommend this tool/technology for use on other types of farm?**
 Maybe, scale is required to justify investment

- **Additional comments?**

Large initial investment, thus requiring a large flock size to justify the cost.
Can be difficult to get animals into the conveyor therefore requires an additional person working or effective sheepdog which defeats the purpose of labour saving.

Sm@ll Ruminant Technologies

Cost/Benefit Analysis

Tool / Technology: **Water enabled weigh crate**

Analysis prepared by (country): **Israel**

Production type the tool/technology is relevant for: Dairy / Meat / **Both**

Description of the “benchmark” farm for which the analysis is performed:

Country: Israel

Production type:

Mainly outdoors / Housed 0-3 months a year / Housed 4-8 months a year / **Mainly indoors**

Farm grazing area: none

Species: Sheep / Goat- both

Number of animals: 100 lambs, 60-70 sheep and goat

Breed: mix

Number of staff: 1

Costs

Initial set-up

- **Capital costs (Large items e.g. a weigh crate, auto-drafter, etc.):**

€1 - €500 €501- €1,000 €1,001-€2,500 €2,501-€5,000 €5,001-€15,000 > €15,000

- **Individual costs (Smaller items e.g. per tag, per sample, per collar):**

€1 - €20 €21- €50 €51-€200 €201-€500 > €500

- **Equipment leasing costs (if not purchased):**

Annual Monthly Weekly €1 - €50 €51-€200 €201-€500 > €500

- **Lifetime of the technology (approximately how long will it last before needing replaced)?**

1 – 4 weeks 1-6 months 6 – 12 months 1-2 years 2-5 years > 5 years

- **Farm infrastructure requirements:** Decrease Increase No change

- **Percentage of animals within the flock/herd that use/are equipped/take advantage of the technology? 100 %**

Running costs

- **Power source requirements (tick all that apply):**

Not required Mains Battery Solar Other

- **Subscription fee – Needed? Yes / No**

- If yes

Per flock / herd <input type="checkbox"/>	Per individual animal <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Per unit <input type="checkbox"/>
Annual <input type="checkbox"/>	Monthly <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Weekly <input type="checkbox"/>
€1 - €50 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	€51 - €200 <input type="checkbox"/>	€201 - €500 <input type="checkbox"/>
		Over €500 <input type="checkbox"/>

- **Additional licences or permits required? No / Yes – Annual / Yes – Monthly / Yes - Weekly**

If yes, cost: €1 - €50 €51 - €200 €201 - €500 Over €500

- **Maintenance cost – included in the subscription? Yes / No / Not applicable**

If no, cost per month: €1 - €50 €51 - €200 €201 - €500 Over €500

- **Maintenance / replacement parts:**

Easy to obtain Difficult to obtain Not obtainable Don't know

- **Technical / mechanical support provided on farm, after purchase? Yes / No**

Training requirements

- **Training required to install / use? Yes / No**

If yes, time range? Up to an hour Half day Full day More

- **Additional technical advice required (e.g. advisor time)? Yes / No**

- **Are there additional costs associated with training and/or technical advice? Yes / No**

Benefits (tick all that apply)

Management

- Labour / time saving.
- Accuracy of records (health, management, movements etc.).
- Management decisions for animal groupings.
- Better individual animal management.
- Improved medicine use.
- Better nutrition / meeting requirements better.
- Improved use of feed resource (grazing, concentrates, etc.).
- Product quality improvements (e.g. hay, carcass, growth, milk, etc.).
- Increased information on production system.
- Opportunity for sharing / moving device (more than one location).

Animal

- Reduced stress to the animal(s).
- Improved welfare of the animals(s).
- Additional information on animal behaviour.
- Information on water intake / water availability.
- Information on food intake / food availability.

Technical

- Compatibility with other devices.
- Ease of data transfer to other software.
- Easy to use once installed.

Other

- Reduced stress to farmer / staff.
- Environmental benefits (e.g. reduced wastage, improved biodiversity, etc.)
- Helps to attract new entrants into the small ruminant industries.

Another benefit not listed? Please give details:

Overall summary:

- **Ease of use?** *Scale 1 (Complicated) – 10 (Simple)*
1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 **10**

- **Value for money (for this type of benchmark farm)?** **Yes** / No / Maybe

- **Recommend this tool/technology for use on other types of farm?**
Yes / No / **Maybe**

- **Additional comments?**

Cost/Benefit Analysis

Tool / Technology: **DCC Delaval Cell Counter**

Analysis prepared by (country): **Italy**

Production type the tool/technology is relevant for: **Dairy** / Meat / Both

Description of the “benchmark” farm for which the analysis is performed:

Country: Italy

Production type:

Mainly outdoors / Housed 0-3 months a year / Housed 4-8 months a year / Mainly indoors

Farm grazing area: 300

Species: **Sheep** / Goat

Number of animals: 800

Breed: Sarda

Number of staff: 6

Costs

Initial set-up

- **Capital costs (Large items e.g. a weigh crate, auto-drafter, etc.):**

€1 - €500 €501- €1,000 €1,001-€2,500 €2,501-€5,000 €5,001-€15,000 > €15,000

- **Individual costs (Smaller items e.g. per tag, per sample, per collar):**

€1 - €20 €21- €50 €51-€200 €201-€500 > €500

- **Equipment leasing costs (if not purchased):**

Annual Monthly Weekly €1 - €50 €51-€200 €201-€500 > €500

- **Lifetime of the technology (approximately how long will it last before needing replaced)?**

1 – 4 weeks 1-6 months 6 – 12 months 1-2 years 2-5 years > 5 years

- **Farm infrastructure requirements:** Decrease Increase No change

- **Percentage of animals within the flock/herd that use/are equipped/take advantage of the technology? 100%**

Running costs

- **Power source requirements (tick all that apply):**

Not required Mains Battery Solar Other

- **Subscription fee – Needed? Yes / No**

○ If yes

Per flock / herd <input type="checkbox"/>	Per individual animal <input type="checkbox"/>	Per unit <input type="checkbox"/>
Annual <input type="checkbox"/>	Monthly <input type="checkbox"/>	Weekly <input type="checkbox"/>
€1 - €50 <input type="checkbox"/>	€51 - €200 <input type="checkbox"/>	€201 - €500 <input type="checkbox"/>
		Over €500 <input type="checkbox"/>

- **Additional licences or permits required? No / Yes – Annual / Yes – Monthly / Yes - Weekly**

If yes, cost: €1 - €50 €51 - €200 €201 - €500 Over €500

- **Maintenance cost – included in the subscription? Yes / No / Not applicable**

If no, cost per month: €1 - €50 €51 - €200 €201 - €500 Over €500

- **Maintenance / replacement parts:**

Easy to obtain Difficult to obtain Not obtainable Don't know

- **Technical / mechanical support provided on farm, after purchase? Yes / No**

Training requirements

- **Training required to install / use? Yes / No**

If yes, time range? Up to an hour Half day Full day More

- **Additional technical advice required (e.g. advisor time)? Yes / No**

- **Are there additional costs associated with training and/or technical advice? Yes / No**

Benefits (tick all that apply)

Management

- Labour / time saving.
- Accuracy of records (health, management, movements etc.).
- Management decisions for animal groupings.
- Better individual animal management.
- Improved medicine use.
- Better nutrition / meeting requirements better.
- Improved use of feed resource (grazing, concentrates, etc.).
- Product quality improvements (e.g. hay, carcass, growth, milk, etc.).
- Increased information on production system.
- Opportunity for sharing / moving device (more than one location).

Animal

- Reduced stress to the animal(s).
- Improved welfare of the animals(s).
- Additional information on animal behaviour.
- Information on water intake / water availability.
- Information on food intake / food availability.

Technical

- Compatibility with other devices.
- Ease of data transfer to other software.
- Easy to use once installed.

Other

- Reduced stress to farmer / staff.
- Environmental benefits (e.g. reduced wastage, improved biodiversity, etc.)
- Helps to attract new entrants into the small ruminant industries.

Another benefit not listed? Please give details:

Overall summary:

- **Ease of use?** *Scale 1 (Complicated) – 10 (Simple)*
1 2 3 4 5 6 7 **8** 9 10

- **Value for money (for this type of benchmark farm)?** Yes / No / **Maybe**

- **Recommend this tool/technology for use on other types of farm?**
Yes / No / **Maybe**

- **Additional comments?**

Sm@ll Ruminant Technologies

Cost/Benefit Analysis

Tool / Technology: **Milk Flowmeters**

Analysis prepared by (country): **Italy**

Production type the tool/technology is relevant for: **Dairy** / Meat / Both

Description of the “benchmark” farm for which the analysis is performed:

Country: Italy

Production type:

Mainly outdoors / Housed 0-3 months a year / Housed 4-8 months a year / Mainly indoors

Farm grazing area: 300

Species: **Sheep** / Goat

Number of animals: 800

Breed: Sarda

Number of staff: 6

Costs

Initial set-up

- **Capital costs (Large items e.g. a weigh crate, auto-drafter, etc.):**

€1 - €500 €501- €1,000 €1,001-€2,500 €2,501-€5,000 €5,001-€15,000 > €15,000

- **Individual costs (Smaller items e.g. per tag, per sample, per collar):**

€1 - €20 €21- €50 €51-€200 €201-€500 > €500

- **Equipment leasing costs (if not purchased):**

Annual Monthly Weekly €1 - €50 €51-€200 €201-€500 > €500

- **Lifetime of the technology (approximately how long will it last before needing replaced)?**

1 – 4 weeks 1-6 months 6 – 12 months 1-2 years 2-5 years > 5 years

- **Farm infrastructure requirements:** Decrease Increase No change

- **Percentage of animals within the flock/herd that use/are equipped/take advantage of the technology? 100%**

Running costs

- **Power source requirements (tick all that apply):**

Not required Mains Battery Solar Other

- **Subscription fee – Needed? Yes / No**

○ If yes

Per flock / herd <input type="checkbox"/>	Per individual animal <input type="checkbox"/>	Per unit <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Annual <input type="checkbox"/>	Monthly <input type="checkbox"/>	Weekly <input type="checkbox"/>
€1 - €50 <input type="checkbox"/>	€51 - €200 <input type="checkbox"/>	€201 - €500 <input type="checkbox"/>
		Over €500 <input type="checkbox"/>

- **Additional licences or permits required? No / Yes – Annual / Yes – Monthly / Yes - Weekly**

If yes, cost: €1 - €50 €51 - €200 €201 - €500 Over €500

- **Maintenance cost – included in the subscription? Yes / No / Not applicable**

If no, cost per month: €1 - €50 €51 - €200 €201 - €500 Over €500

- **Maintenance / replacement parts:**

Easy to obtain Difficult to obtain Not obtainable Don't know

- **Technical / mechanical support provided on farm, after purchase? Yes / No**

Training requirements

- **Training required to install / use? Yes / No**

If yes, time range? Up to an hour Half day Full day More

- **Additional technical advice required (e.g. advisor time)? Yes / No**

- **Are there additional costs associated with training and/or technical advice? Yes / No**

Benefits (tick all that apply)

Management

- Labour / time saving.
- Accuracy of records (health, management, movements etc.).
- Management decisions for animal groupings.
- Better individual animal management.
- Improved medicine use.
- Better nutrition / meeting requirements better.
- Improved use of feed resource (grazing, concentrates, etc.).
- Product quality improvements (e.g. hay, carcass, growth, milk, etc.).
- Increased information on production system.
- Opportunity for sharing / moving device (more than one location).

Animal

- Reduced stress to the animal(s).
- Improved welfare of the animals(s).
- Additional information on animal behaviour.
- Information on water intake / water availability.
- Information on food intake / food availability.

Technical

- Compatibility with other devices.
- Ease of data transfer to other software.
- Easy to use once installed.

Other

- Reduced stress to farmer / staff.
- Environmental benefits (e.g. reduced wastage, improved biodiversity, etc.)
- Helps to attract new entrants into the small ruminant industries.

Another benefit not listed? Please give details:

Overall summary:

- **Ease of use?** *Scale 1 (Complicated) – 10 (Simple)*
1 2 3 4 5 **6** 7 8 9 10

- **Value for money (for this type of benchmark farm)?** Yes / No / **Maybe**

- **Recommend this tool/technology for use on other types of farm?**
Yes / No / **Maybe**

- **Additional comments?**

Sm@ll Ruminant Technologies

Cost/Benefit Analysis

Tool / Technology: **Portable NIRS (Near infra-red spectroscopy)**

Analysis prepared by (country): **Italy**

Production type the tool/technology is relevant for: Dairy / Meat / **Both**

Description of the “benchmark” farm for which the analysis is performed:

Country: Italy

Production type:

Mainly outdoors / Housed 0-3 months a year / Housed 4-8 months a year / **Mainly indoors**

Farm grazing area: 100

Species: **Sheep** / Goat

Number of animals: 300

Breed: Sarda

Number of staff: 2

Costs

Initial set-up

- **Capital costs (Large items e.g. a weigh crate, auto-drafter, etc.):**

€1 - €500 €501- €1,000 €1,001-€2,500 €2,501-€5,000 €5,001-€15,000 > €15,000

- **Individual costs (Smaller items e.g. per tag, per sample, per collar):**

€1 - €20 €21- €50 €51-€200 €201-€500 > €500

- **Equipment leasing costs (if not purchased):**

Annual Monthly Weekly €1 - €50 €51-€200 €201-€500 > €500

- **Lifetime of the technology (approximately how long will it last before needing replaced)?**

1 – 4 weeks 1-6 months 6 – 12 months 1-2 years 2-5 years > 5 years

- **Farm infrastructure requirements:** Decrease Increase No change

- **Percentage of animals within the flock/herd that use/are equipped/take advantage of the technology? 100%**

Running costs

- **Power source requirements (tick all that apply):**

Not required Mains Battery Solar Other

- **Subscription fee – Needed? Yes / No**

○ If yes

Per flock / herd <input type="checkbox"/>	Per individual animal <input type="checkbox"/>	Per unit <input type="checkbox"/>
Annual <input type="checkbox"/>	Monthly <input type="checkbox"/>	Weekly <input type="checkbox"/>
€1 - €50 <input type="checkbox"/>	€51 - €200 <input type="checkbox"/>	€201 - €500 <input type="checkbox"/>
		Over €500 <input type="checkbox"/>

- **Additional licences or permits required? No / Yes – Annual / Yes – Monthly / Yes - Weekly**

If yes, cost: €1 - €50 €51 - €200 €201 - €500 Over €500

- **Maintenance cost – included in the subscription? Yes / No / Not applicable**

If no, cost per month: €1 - €50 €51 - €200 €201 - €500 Over €500

- **Maintenance / replacement parts:**

Easy to obtain Difficult to obtain Not obtainable Don't know

- **Technical / mechanical support provided on farm, after purchase? Yes / No**

Training requirements

- **Training required to install / use? Yes / No**

If yes, time range? Up to an hour Half day Full day More

- **Additional technical advice required (e.g. advisor time)? Yes / No**

- **Are there additional costs associated with training and/or technical advice? Yes / No**

Benefits (tick all that apply)

Management

- Labour / time saving.
- Accuracy of records (health, management, movements etc.).
- Management decisions for animal groupings.
- Better individual animal management.
- Improved medicine use.
- Better nutrition / meeting requirements better.
- Improved use of feed resource (grazing, concentrates, etc.).
- Product quality improvements (e.g. hay, carcass, growth, milk, etc.).
- Increased information on production system.
- Opportunity for sharing / moving device (more than one location).

Animal

- Reduced stress to the animal(s).
- Improved welfare of the animals(s).
- Additional information on animal behaviour.
- Information on water intake / water availability.
- Information on food intake / food availability.

Technical

- Compatibility with other devices.
- Ease of data transfer to other software.
- Easy to use once installed.

Other

- Reduced stress to farmer / staff.
- Environmental benefits (e.g. reduced wastage, improved biodiversity, etc.)
- Helps to attract new entrants into the small ruminant industries.

Another benefit not listed? Please give details:

Overall summary:

- **Ease of use?** *Scale 1 (Complicated) – 10 (Simple)*
1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 **9** 10

- **Value for money (for this type of benchmark farm)?** Yes / No / **Maybe**

- **Recommend this tool/technology for use on other types of farm?**
Yes / No / **Maybe**

- **Additional comments?**

Sm@ll Ruminant Technologies

Cost/Benefit Analysis

Tool / Technology: **Weather station + Fan cooler**

Analysis prepared by (country): **Italy**

Production type the tool/technology is relevant for: Dairy / Meat / **Both**

Description of the “benchmark” farm for which the analysis is performed:

Country: Italy

Production type:

Mainly outdoors / Housed 0-3 months a year / Housed 4-8 months a year / **Mainly indoors**

Farm grazing area:

Species: **Sheep** / Goat

Number of animals: 50

Breed: Sarda

Number of staff: 1.5

Costs

Initial set-up

- **Capital costs (Large items e.g. a weigh crate, auto-drafter, etc.):**

€1 - €500 €501- €1,000 €1,001-€2,500 €2,501-€5,000 €5,001-€15,000 > €15,000

- **Individual costs (Smaller items e.g. per tag, per sample, per collar):**

€1 - €20 €21- €50 €51-€200 €201-€500 > €500

- **Equipment leasing costs (if not purchased):**

Annual Monthly Weekly €1 - €50 €51-€200 €201-€500 > €500

- **Lifetime of the technology (approximately how long will it last before needing replaced)?**

1 – 4 weeks 1-6 months 6 – 12 months 1-2 years 2-5 years > 5 years

- **Farm infrastructure requirements:** Decrease Increase No change

- **Percentage of animals within the flock/herd that use/are equipped/take advantage of the technology? 100%**

Running costs

- **Power source requirements (tick all that apply):**

Not required Mains Battery Solar Other

- **Subscription fee – Needed? Yes / No**

○ If yes

Per flock / herd <input type="checkbox"/>	Per individual animal <input type="checkbox"/>	Per unit <input type="checkbox"/>
Annual <input type="checkbox"/>	Monthly <input type="checkbox"/>	Weekly <input type="checkbox"/>
€1 - €50 <input type="checkbox"/>	€51 - €200 <input type="checkbox"/>	€201 - €500 <input type="checkbox"/> Over €500 <input type="checkbox"/>

- **Additional licences or permits required? No / Yes – Annual / Yes – Monthly / Yes - Weekly**

If yes, cost: €1 - €50 €51 - €200 €201 - €500 Over €500

- **Maintenance cost – included in the subscription? Yes / No / Not applicable**

If no, cost per month: €1 - €50 €51 - €200 €201 - €500 Over €500

- **Maintenance / replacement parts:**

Easy to obtain Difficult to obtain Not obtainable Don't know

- **Technical / mechanical support provided on farm, after purchase? Yes / No**

Training requirements

- **Training required to install / use? Yes / No**

If yes, time range? Up to an hour Half day Full day More

- **Additional technical advice required (e.g. advisor time)? Yes / No**

- **Are there additional costs associated with training and/or technical advice? Yes / No**

Benefits (tick all that apply)

Management

- Labour / time saving.
- Accuracy of records (health, management, movements etc.).
- Management decisions for animal groupings.
- Better individual animal management.
- Improved medicine use.
- Better nutrition / meeting requirements better.
- Improved use of feed resource (grazing, concentrates, etc.).
- Product quality improvements (e.g. hay, carcass, growth, milk, etc.).
- Increased information on production system.
- Opportunity for sharing / moving device (more than one location).

Animal

- Reduced stress to the animal(s).
- Improved welfare of the animals(s).
- Additional information on animal behaviour.
- Information on water intake / water availability.
- Information on food intake / food availability.

Technical

- Compatibility with other devices.
- Ease of data transfer to other software.
- Easy to use once installed.

Other

- Reduced stress to farmer / staff.
- Environmental benefits (e.g. reduced wastage, improved biodiversity, etc.)
- Helps to attract new entrants into the small ruminant industries.

Another benefit not listed? Please give details:

Overall summary:

- **Ease of use?** *Scale 1 (Complicated) – 10 (Simple)*
1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

- **Value for money (for this type of benchmark farm)?** Yes / No / Maybe

- **Recommend this tool/technology for use on other types of farm?**
 Yes / No / Maybe

- **Additional comments?**

Cost/Benefit Analysis

Tool / Technology: **EID-enabled weigh crate**

Analysis prepared by (country): **UK**

Production type the tool/technology is relevant for: Dairy / Meat / **Both**

Description of the “benchmark” farm for which the analysis is performed:

Country: UK

Production type:

Mainly outdoors / Housed 0-3 months a year / Housed 4-8 months a year / Mainly indoors

Farm grazing area: ~1,000 ha

Species: **Sheep** / Goat

Number of animals: 700 ewes

Breed: Predominantly Scottish Blackface

Number of staff: 2

Costs

Initial set-up

- **Capital costs (Large items e.g. a weigh crate, auto-drafter, etc.):**

€1 - €500 €501- €1,000 €1,001-€2,500 €2,501-€5,000 €5,001-€15,000 > €15,000

- **Individual costs (Smaller items e.g. per tag, per sample, per collar):**

€1 - €20 €21- €50 €51-€200 €201-€500 > €500

- **Equipment leasing costs (if not purchased):**

Annual Monthly Weekly €1 - €50 €51-€200 €201-€500 > €500

- **Lifetime of the technology (approximately how long will it last before needing replaced)?**

1 – 4 weeks 1-6 months 6 – 12 months 1-2 years 2-5 years > 5 years

- **Farm infrastructure requirements:** Decrease Increase No change

- **Percentage of animals within the flock/herd that use/are equipped/take advantage of the technology? 100 %**

Running costs

- **Power source requirements (tick all that apply):**

Not required Mains Battery Solar Other

- **Subscription fee – Needed? Yes / **No****

- **If yes**

Per flock / herd <input type="checkbox"/>	Per individual animal <input type="checkbox"/>	Per unit <input type="checkbox"/>
Annual <input type="checkbox"/>	Monthly <input type="checkbox"/>	Weekly <input type="checkbox"/>
€1 - €50 <input type="checkbox"/>	€51 - €200 <input type="checkbox"/>	€201 - €500 <input type="checkbox"/>
		Over €500 <input type="checkbox"/>

- **Additional licences or permits required? **No** Yes – Annual / Yes – Monthly / Yes - Weekly**

If yes, cost: €1 - €50 €51 - €200 €201 - €500 Over €500

- **Maintenance cost – included in the subscription? Yes / **No** / Not applicable**

If no, cost per month: €1 - €50 €51 - €200 €201 - €500 Over €500

- **Maintenance / replacement parts:**

Easy to obtain Difficult to obtain Not obtainable Don't know

- **Technical / mechanical support provided on farm, after purchase? Yes / **No****

Training requirements

- **Training required to install / use? **Yes** No**

If yes, time range? Up to an hour Half day Full day More

- **Additional technical advice required (e.g. advisor time)? **Yes** No**

- **Are there additional costs associated with training and/or technical advice? **Yes** No**

Benefits (tick all that apply)

Management

- Labour / time saving.
- Accuracy of records (health, management, movements etc.).
- Management decisions for animal groupings.
- Better individual animal management.
- Improved medicine use.
- Better nutrition / meeting requirements better.
- Improved use of feed resource (grazing, concentrates, etc.).
- Product quality improvements (e.g. hay, carcass, growth, milk, etc.).
- Increased information on production system.
- Opportunity for sharing / moving device (more than one location).

Animal

- Reduced stress to the animal(s).
- Improved welfare of the animals(s).
- Additional information on animal behaviour.
- Information on water intake / water availability.
- Information on food intake / food availability.

Technical

- Compatibility with other devices.
- Ease of data transfer to other software.
- Easy to use once installed.

Other

- Reduced stress to farmer / staff.
- Environmental benefits (e.g. reduced wastage, improved biodiversity, etc.)
- Helps to attract new entrants into the small ruminant industries.

Another benefit not listed? Please give details:

Helps to collect individual animal data – performance, presence/absence, health etc.
Welfare benefits – early warning of something wrong based on weight changes.
Useful for recording data for genetic improvement programmes.
Provides an automatic way to identify animals to be culled later in the year – bad lambing, poor mothers, consistently lame etc. (instead of having to use paper records).
Allows farmers to use methods such as the Targeted Selective Treatment (TST) method for worming.

Overall summary:

- **Ease of use?** *Scale 1 (Complicated) – 10 (Simple)*

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 **8** 9 10

- **Value for money (for this type of benchmark farm)?** Yes / ~~No~~ / ~~Maybe~~

- **Recommend this tool/technology for use on other types of farm?**

Yes / ~~No~~ / ~~Maybe~~

- **Additional comments?**

All animals must be tagged with an EID tag to make full use of the weight crate capabilities, therefore tagging lambs as early as possible is worthwhile.

Large initial cost but benefits have been quantified in terms of saved labour and reduced medicine use (just two examples). It will pay for itself after a few years.

There are a range of products available on the market. Simpler versions include using a manual weigh crate combined with an EID-stick and weigh-head. More sophisticated versions include the use of an auto-drafter and a higher specification weigh-head. There are also fixed position and mobile versions available as well.

Sm@ll Ruminant Technologies

Cost/Benefit Analysis

Tool / Technology: **DNA parentage**

Analysis prepared by (country): **UK**

Production type the tool/technology is relevant for: Dairy / Meat / **Both**

Description of the “benchmark” farm for which the analysis is performed:

Country: UK

Production type:

Mainly outdoors / Housed 0-3 months a year / Housed 4-8 months a year / Mainly indoors

Farm grazing area: ~1,000 ha

Species: **Sheep** / Goat

Number of animals: 700 ewes

Breed: Predominantly Scottish Blackface

Number of staff: 2

Costs

Initial set-up

- **Capital costs (Large items e.g. a weigh crate, auto-drafter, etc.):**
 €1 - €500 €501- €1,000 €1,001-€2,500 €2,501-€5,000 €5,001-€15,000 > €15,000
- **Individual costs (Smaller items e.g. per tag, per sample, per collar):**
 €1 - €20 €21- €50 €51-€200 €201-€500 > €500
- **Equipment leasing costs (if not purchased):**
 Annual Monthly Weekly €1 - €50 €51-€200 €201-€500 > €500
- **Lifetime of the technology (approximately how long will it last before needing replaced)?**
 1 – 4 weeks 1-6 months 6 – 12 months 1-2 years 2-5 years > 5 years
- **Farm infrastructure requirements:** Decrease Increase No change
- **Percentage of animals within the flock/herd that use/are equipped/take advantage of the technology?** 100 %

Running costs

- **Power source requirements (tick all that apply):**
 Not required Mains Battery Solar Other
- **Subscription fee – Needed?** Yes / **No**
 - If yes

Per flock / herd <input type="checkbox"/>	Per individual animal <input type="checkbox"/>	Per unit <input type="checkbox"/>	
Annual <input type="checkbox"/>	Monthly <input type="checkbox"/>	Weekly <input type="checkbox"/>	
€1 - €50 <input type="checkbox"/>	€51 - €200 <input type="checkbox"/>	€201 - €500 <input type="checkbox"/>	Over €500 <input type="checkbox"/>
- **Additional licences or permits required?** **No** Yes – Annual / Yes – Monthly / Yes - Weekly
 If yes, cost:

€1 - €50 <input type="checkbox"/>	€51 - €200 <input type="checkbox"/>	€201 - €500 <input type="checkbox"/>	Over €500 <input type="checkbox"/>
-----------------------------------	-------------------------------------	--------------------------------------	------------------------------------
- **Maintenance cost – included in the subscription?** Yes / No **Not applicable**
 If no, cost per month: €1 - €50 €51 - €200 €201 - €500 Over €500
- **Maintenance / replacement parts:**
 Easy to obtain Difficult to obtain Not obtainable Don't know
- **Technical / mechanical support provided on farm, after purchase?** Yes / **No**

Training requirements

- **Training required to install / use?** **Yes** No
 If yes, time range? Up to an hour Half day Full day More
- **Additional technical advice required (e.g. advisor time)?** **Yes** No
- **Are there additional costs associated with training and/or technical advice?** Yes / **No**

Benefits (tick all that apply)

Management

- Labour / time saving.
- Accuracy of records (health, management, movements etc.).
- Management decisions for animal groupings.
- Better individual animal management.
- Improved medicine use.
- Better nutrition / meeting requirements better.
- Improved use of feed resource (grazing, concentrates, etc.).
- Product quality improvements (e.g. hay, carcass, growth, milk, etc.).
- Increased information on production system.
- Opportunity for sharing / moving device (more than one location).

Animal

- Reduced stress to the animal(s).
- Improved welfare of the animals(s).
- Additional information on animal behaviour.
- Information on water intake / water availability.
- Information on food intake / food availability.

Technical

- Compatibility with other devices.
- Ease of data transfer to other software.
- Easy to use once installed.

Other

- Reduced stress to farmer / staff.
- Environmental benefits (e.g. reduced wastage, improved biodiversity, etc.)
- Helps to attract new entrants into the small ruminant industries.

Another benefit not listed? Please give details:

Helps to assess ewe, ram & lamb performance.

Ability to collect data for genetic improvement programmes.

Allows the use of multi-sire mating groups (rather than single sire groups / artificial insemination)

Less labour required at lambing time for recording.

Overall summary:

- **Ease of use?** *Scale 1 (Complicated) – 10 (Simple)*

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 **9** 10

- **Value for money (for this type of benchmark farm)?** Yes / ~~No~~ / ~~Maybe~~

- **Recommend this tool/technology for use on other types of farm?**

Yes / ~~No~~ / ~~Maybe~~

- **Additional comments?**

Large initial cost of sampling every animal in the flock, but yearly costs thereafter only include lambs born each year and any new animals joining the flock.

Only useful if the data (pedigree information) is going to be used.

Horizon 2020
Programme

Sm@ll Ruminant Technologies

Cost/Benefit Analysis

Tool / Technology: **Automatic grass plate meters**

Analysis prepared by (country): **UK**

Production type the tool/technology is relevant for: Dairy / Meat / **Both**

Description of the “benchmark” farm for which the analysis is performed:

Country: UK

Production type:

Mainly outdoors / Housed 0-3 months a year / Housed 4-8 months a year / Mainly indoors

Farm grazing area: ~1,000 ha

Species: **Sheep** / Goat

Number of animals: 700 ewes

Breed: Predominantly Scottish Blackface

Number of staff: 2

Costs

Initial set-up

- **Capital costs (Large items e.g. a weigh crate, auto-drafter, etc.):**

€1 - €500 €501- €1,000 €1,001-€2,500 €2,501-€5,000 €5,001-€15,000 > €15,000

- **Individual costs (Smaller items e.g. per tag, per sample, per collar):**

€1 - €20 €21- €50 €51-€200 €201-€500 > €500

- **Equipment leasing costs (if not purchased):**

Annual Monthly Weekly €1 - €50 €51-€200 €201-€500 > €500

- **Lifetime of the technology (approximately how long will it last before needing replaced)?**

1 – 4 weeks 1-6 months 6 – 12 months 1-2 years 2-5 years > 5 years

- **Farm infrastructure requirements:** Decrease Increase No change

- **Percentage of animals within the flock/herd that use/are equipped/take advantage of the technology? 100 %**

Running costs

- **Power source requirements (tick all that apply):**

Not required Mains Battery Solar Other

- **Subscription fee – Needed? Yes / **No****

- If yes

Per flock / herd <input type="checkbox"/>	Per individual animal <input type="checkbox"/>	Per unit <input type="checkbox"/>
Annual <input type="checkbox"/>	Monthly <input type="checkbox"/>	Weekly <input type="checkbox"/>
€1 - €50 <input type="checkbox"/>	€51 - €200 <input type="checkbox"/>	€201 - €500 <input type="checkbox"/> Over €500 <input type="checkbox"/>

- **Additional licences or permits required? **No** Yes – Annual / Yes – Monthly / Yes - Weekly**

If yes, cost: €1 - €50 €51 - €200 €201 - €500 Over €500

- **Maintenance cost – included in the subscription? Yes / **No** / Not applicable**

If no, cost per month: €1 - €50 €51 - €200 €201 - €500 Over €500

- **Maintenance / replacement parts:**

Easy to obtain Difficult to obtain Not obtainable Don't know

- **Technical / mechanical support provided on farm, after purchase? Yes / **No****

Training requirements

- **Training required to install / use? **Yes** / No**

If yes, time range? Up to an hour Half day Full day More

- **Additional technical advice required (e.g. advisor time)? Yes / **No****

- **Are there additional costs associated with training and/or technical advice? Yes / **No****

Benefits (tick all that apply)

Management

- Labour / time saving.
- Accuracy of records (health, management, movements etc.).
- Management decisions for animal groupings.
- Better individual animal management.
- Improved medicine use.
- Better nutrition / meeting requirements better.
- Improved use of feed resource (grazing, concentrates, etc.).
- Product quality improvements (e.g. hay, carcass, growth, milk, etc.).
- Increased information on production system.
- Opportunity for sharing / moving device (more than one location).

Animal

- Reduced stress to the animal(s).
- Improved welfare of the animals(s).
- Additional information on animal behaviour.
- Information on water intake / water availability.
- Information on food intake / food availability.

Technical

- Compatibility with other devices.
- Ease of data transfer to other software.
- Easy to use once installed.

Other

- Reduced stress to farmer / staff.
- Environmental benefits (e.g. reduced wastage, improved biodiversity, etc.)
- Helps to attract new entrants into the small ruminant industries.

Another benefit not listed? Please give details:

Useful for rotational grazing systems.

Allows farmers to plan for when there is a lot, or very little, grass available.

Data helps to plan when additional supplementation is required.

Overall summary:

- **Ease of use?** *Scale 1 (Complicated) – 10 (Simple)*

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 **8** 9 10

- **Value for money (for this type of benchmark farm)?** Yes / ~~No~~ / ~~Maybe~~

- **Recommend this tool/technology for use on other types of farm?**

Yes / ~~No~~ / ~~Maybe~~

- **Additional comments?**

Mainly useful for improved and/or semi-improved grazing. Might not be so practical for extensive hill ground grazing.

Data collected can be used with some mobile phone apps and farm management software (some of these may involve a subscription fee). Alternatively, data can be used in grazing calculators such as those provided by Quality Meat Scotland (QMS) [[QMS Grazing Calculator \(qmscotland.co.uk\)](https://qmscotland.co.uk)] or the Agriculture and Horticulture Development Board (AHDB) [[Feed \(grass and supplementation\) budget planner | AHDB](#)] – UK examples.

Horizon 2020
Programme

Cost/Benefit Analysis

Tool: **Autodrafter**

Analysis prepared by (country): **Hungary**

Production type the tool/technology is relevant for: Both

Description of the “benchmark” farm for which the analysis is performed:

Country: Hungary

Production type:

Mainly outdoors / Housed 0-3 months a year / Housed 4-8 months a year / Mainly indoors

Farm grazing area:

Species: Sheep / Goat

Number of animals: 300

Breed: tsigai, dorper

Number of staff: 6

Costs

Initial set-up

- **Capital costs (Large items e.g. a weigh crate, auto-drafter, etc.):**

€1 - €500 €501- €1,000 €1,001-€2,500 €2,501-€5,000 €5,001-€15,000 > €15,000

- **Individual costs (Smaller items e.g. per tag, per sample, per collar):**

€1 - €20 €21- €50 €51-€200 €201-€500 > €500

- **Equipment leasing costs (if not purchased):**

Annual Monthly Weekly €1 - €50 €51-€200 €201-€500 > €500

- **Lifetime of the technology (approximately how long will it last before needing replaced)?**

1 – 4 weeks 1-6 months 6 – 12 months 1-2 years 2-5 years > 5 years

- **Farm infrastructure requirements:** Decrease Increase No change

- **Percentage of animals within the flock/herd that use/are equipped/take advantage of the technology? 100%**

Running costs

- **Power source requirements (tick all that apply):**

Not required Mains Battery Solar Other

- **Subscription fee – Needed? Yes / No**

- **If yes**

Per flock / herd <input type="checkbox"/>	Per individual animal <input type="checkbox"/>	Per unit <input type="checkbox"/>
Annual <input type="checkbox"/>	Monthly <input type="checkbox"/>	Weekly <input type="checkbox"/>
€1 - €50 <input type="checkbox"/>	€51 - €200 <input type="checkbox"/>	€201 - €500 <input type="checkbox"/>
		Over €500 <input type="checkbox"/>

- **Additional licences or permits required? No / Yes – Annual / Yes – Monthly / Yes - Weekly**

If yes, cost: €1 - €50 €51 - €200 €201 - €500 Over €500

- **Maintenance cost – included in the subscription? Yes / No / Not applicable**

If no, cost per month: €1 - €50 €51 - €200 €201 - €500 Over €500

- **Maintenance / replacement parts:**

Easy to obtain Difficult to obtain Not obtainable Don't know

- **Technical / mechanical support provided on farm, after purchase? Yes / No**

Training requirements

- **Training required to install / use? Yes / No**

If yes, time range? Up to an hour Half day Full day More

- **Additional technical advice required (e.g. advisor time)? Yes / No**

- **Are there additional costs associated with training and/or technical advice? Yes / No**

Benefits (tick all that apply)

Management

- Labour / time saving.
- Accuracy of records (health, management, movements etc.).
- Management decisions for animal groupings.
- Better individual animal management.
- Improved medicine use.
- Better nutrition / meeting requirements better.
- Improved use of feed resource (grazing, concentrates, etc.).
- Product quality improvements (e.g. hay, carcass, growth, milk, etc.).
- Increased information on production system.
- Opportunity for sharing / moving device (more than one location).

Animal

- Reduced stress to the animal(s).
- Improved welfare of the animals(s).
- Additional information on animal behaviour.
- Information on water intake / water availability.
- Information on food intake / food availability.

Technical

- Compatibility with other devices.
- Ease of data transfer to other software.
- Easy to use once installed.

Other

- Reduced stress to farmer / staff.
- Environmental benefits (e.g. reduced wastage, improved biodiversity, etc.)
- Helps to attract new entrants into the small ruminant industries.

Another benefit not listed? Please give details:

variable usage - It can be mobile or permanently fixed in position

Overall summary:

- **Ease of use?** *Scale 1 (Complicated) – 10 (Simple)*
1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10
- **Value for money (for this type of benchmark farm)?** Yes / No / Maybe
- **Recommend this tool/technology for use on other types of farm?**
Yes / No / Maybe
- **Additional comments?**

The investment cost is high, but it's really useful for bigger flocks.

Horizon 2020
Programme

Cost/Benefit Analysis

Tool / Technology: **EID stick reader**

Analysis prepared by (country): **Ireland**

Production type the tool/technology is relevant for: Both

Description of the “benchmark” farm for which the analysis is performed:

Country: *Ireland*

Production type:

Housed 0-3 months a year – Meat sheep

Farm grazing area: *35ha*

Species: *Sheep*

Number of animals: *300 ewes plus their lambs and replacements*

Breed: *Suffolk x Belclare*

Number of staff: *1 farmer*

Costs

Initial set-up

- **Capital costs (Large items e.g. a weigh crate, auto-drafter, etc.):**

€1 - €500 €501- €1,000 €1,001-€2,500 €2,501-€5,000 €5,001-€15,000 > €15,000

- **Individual costs (Smaller items e.g. per tag, per sample, per collar):**

€1 - €20 €21- €50 €51-€200 €201-€500 > €500

- **Equipment leasing costs (if not purchased):**

Annual Monthly Weekly €1 - €50 €51-€200 €201-€500 > €500

- **Lifetime of the technology (approximately how long will it last before needing replaced)?**

1 – 4 weeks 1-6 months 6 – 12 months 1-2 years 2-5 years > 5 years

- **Farm infrastructure requirements:** Decrease Increase No change

- **Percentage of animals within the flock/herd that use/are equipped/take advantage of the technology?** *100% provided they are EID tagged*

Running costs

- **Power source requirements (tick all that apply): Charger**

Not required Mains Battery Solar Other

- **Subscription fee – No**

- **If yes**

Per flock / herd <input type="checkbox"/>	Per individual animal <input type="checkbox"/>	Per unit <input type="checkbox"/>
Annual <input type="checkbox"/>	Monthly <input type="checkbox"/>	Weekly <input type="checkbox"/>
€1 - €50 <input type="checkbox"/>	€51 - €200 <input type="checkbox"/>	€201 - €500 <input type="checkbox"/>
		Over €500 <input type="checkbox"/>

- **Additional licences or permits required? No**

If yes, cost: €1 - €50 €51 - €200 €201 - €500 Over €500

- **Maintenance cost – included in the subscription? Not applicable**

If no, cost per month: €1 - €50 €51 - €200 €201 - €500 Over €500

- **Maintenance / replacement parts:**

Easy to obtain Difficult to obtain Not obtainable Don't know

- **Technical / mechanical support provided on farm, after purchase? No**

Training requirements

- **Training required to install / use? Yes**

If yes, time range? Up to an hour Half day Full day More

- **Additional technical advice required (e.g. advisor time)? Yes possibly from sales rep**

- **Are there additional costs associated with training and/or technical advice? No**

Benefits (tick all that apply)

Management

- Labour / time saving.
- Accuracy of records (health, management, movements etc.).
- Management decisions for animal groupings.
- Better individual animal management.
- Improved medicine use.
- Better nutrition / meeting requirements better.
- Improved use of feed resource (grazing, concentrates, etc.).
- Product quality improvements (e.g. hay, carcass, growth, milk, etc.).
- Increased information on production system.
- Opportunity for sharing / moving device (more than one location).

Animal

- Reduced stress to the animal(s).
- Improved welfare of the animals(s).
- Additional information on animal behaviour.
- Information on water intake / water availability.
- Information on food intake / food availability.

Technical

- Compatibility with other devices.
- Ease of data transfer to other software.
- Easy to use once installed.

Other

- Reduced stress to farmer / staff.
- Environmental benefits (e.g. reduced wastage, improved biodiversity, etc.)
- Helps to attract new entrants into the small ruminant industries.

Another benefit not listed? Please give details:

Overall summary:

- **Ease of use?** *Scale 1 (Complicated) – 10 (Simple)*
1 2 3 4 **5** 6 7 8 9 10

- **Value for money (for this type of benchmark farm)?** *Yes*

- **Recommend this tool/technology for use on other types of farm?**

 Yes

- **Additional comments?**

Subscription fees may be involved if using with a farm management package - Depends on software used e.g. TGM from €346 lifetime cost for <100 ewes up to €3464 unlimited ewes lifetime cost, alternatively between €20-52/month. Flockwatch costs approximately €95 per year, but some services are free and do not require a subscription. Datamars software is free to use with compatible equipment at the moment.

Sm@ll Ruminant Technologies

Cost/Benefit Analysis

Tool / Technology: **Farm Management Software**

Analysis prepared by (country): **Israel**

Production type the tool/technology is relevant for: **Dairy** / Meat / Both

Description of the “benchmark” farm for which the analysis is performed:

Country: Israel

Production type:

Mainly outdoors / Housed 0-3 months a year / Housed 4-8 months a year / **Mainly indoors**

Farm grazing area:

Species: **Sheep / Goat**

Number of animals: 1300

Breed: x

Number of staff: 4

Costs

Initial set-up

- **Capital costs (Large items e.g. a weigh crate, auto-drafter, etc.):**

€1 - €500 €501- €1,000 €1,001-€2,500 €2,501-€5,000 €5,001-€15,000 > €15,000

- **Individual costs (Smaller items e.g. per tag, per sample, per collar):**

€1 - €20 €21- €50 €51-€200 €201-€500 > €500

- **Equipment leasing costs (if not purchased):**

Annual Monthly Weekly €1 - €50 €51-€200 €201-€500 > €500

- **Lifetime of the technology (approximately how long will it last before needing replaced)?**

1 – 4 weeks 1-6 months 6 – 12 months 1-2 years 2-5 years > 5 years

- **Farm infrastructure requirements:** Decrease Increase No change

- **Percentage of animals within the flock/herd that use/are equipped/take advantage of the technology? 100%**

Running costs

- **Power source requirements (tick all that apply):**

Not required Mains Battery Solar Other

- **Subscription fee – Needed? Yes / No**

- **If yes**

Per flock / herd <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Per individual animal <input type="checkbox"/>	Per unit <input type="checkbox"/>
Annual <input type="checkbox"/>	Monthly <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Weekly <input type="checkbox"/>
€1 - €50 <input type="checkbox"/>	€51 - €200 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	€201 - €500 <input type="checkbox"/>
		Over €500 <input type="checkbox"/>

- **Additional licences or permits required? No / Yes – Annual / Yes – Monthly / Yes - Weekly**

If yes, cost: €1 - €50 €51 - €200 €201 - €500 Over €500

- **Maintenance cost – included in the subscription? Yes / **No** / Not applicable**

If no, cost per month: €1 - €50 €51 - €200 €201 - €500 Over €500

- **Maintenance / replacement parts:**

Easy to obtain Difficult to obtain Not obtainable Don't know

- **Technical / mechanical support provided on farm, after purchase? Yes / No**

Training requirements

- **Training required to install / use? Yes / No**

If yes, time range? Up to an hour Half day Full day More

- **Additional technical advice required (e.g. advisor time)? Yes / **No****

- **Are there additional costs associated with training and/or technical advice? Yes / **No****

Benefits (tick all that apply)

Management

- Labour / time saving.
- Accuracy of records (health, management, movements etc.).
- Management decisions for animal groupings.
- Better individual animal management.
- Improved medicine use.
- Better nutrition / meeting requirements better.
- Improved use of feed resource (grazing, concentrates, etc.).
- Product quality improvements (e.g. hay, carcass, growth, milk, etc.).
- Increased information on production system.
- Opportunity for sharing / moving device (more than one location).

Animal

- Reduced stress to the animal(s).
- Improved welfare of the animals(s).
- Additional information on animal behaviour.
- Information on water intake / water availability.
- Information on food intake / food availability.

Technical

- Compatibility with other devices.
- Ease of data transfer to other software.
- Easy to use once installed.

Other

- Reduced stress to farmer / staff.
- Environmental benefits (e.g. reduced wastage, improved biodiversity, etc.)
- Helps to attract new entrants into the small ruminant industries.

Another benefit not listed? Please give details:

Overall summary:

- **Ease of use?** *Scale 1 (Complicated) – 10 (Simple)*
1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 **10**

- **Value for money (for this type of benchmark farm)?** **Yes** / No / Maybe

- **Recommend this tool/technology for use on other types of farm?**
Yes / No / Maybe

- **Additional comments?**

Sm@ll Ruminant Technologies

Cost/Benefit Analysis

Tool / Technology: Automatic feeders

Analysis prepared by (country): Italy

Production type the tool/technology is relevant for: Dairy / Meat / **Both**

Description of the “benchmark” farm for which the analysis is performed:

Country: Italy

Production type:

Mainly outdoors / Housed 0-3 months a year / Housed 4-8 months a year / **Mainly indoors**

Farm grazing area:

Species: **Sheep** / Goat

Number of animals: 50

Breed: Sarda

Number of staff: 1.5

Costs

Initial set-up

- **Capital costs (Large items e.g. a weigh crate, auto-drafter, etc.):**

€1 - €500 €501- €1,000 €1,001-€2,500 €2,501-€5,000 €5,001-€15,000 > €15,000

- **Individual costs (Smaller items e.g. per tag, per sample, per collar):**

€1 - €20 €21- €50 €51-€200 €201-€500 > €500

- **Equipment leasing costs (if not purchased):**

Annual Monthly Weekly €1 - €50 €51-€200 €201-€500 > €500

- **Lifetime of the technology (approximately how long will it last before needing replaced)?**

1 – 4 weeks 1-6 months 6 – 12 months 1-2 years 2-5 years > 5 years

- **Farm infrastructure requirements:** Decrease Increase No change

- **Percentage of animals within the flock/herd that use/are equipped/take advantage of the technology? 100%**

Running costs

- **Power source requirements (tick all that apply):**

Not required Mains Battery Solar Other

- **Subscription fee – Needed? Yes / No**

○ If yes

Per flock / herd <input type="checkbox"/>	Per individual animal <input type="checkbox"/>	Per unit <input type="checkbox"/>
Annual <input type="checkbox"/>	Monthly <input type="checkbox"/>	Weekly <input type="checkbox"/>
€1 - €50 <input type="checkbox"/>	€51 - €200 <input type="checkbox"/>	€201 - €500 <input type="checkbox"/> Over €500 <input type="checkbox"/>

- **Additional licences or permits required? No / Yes – Annual / Yes – Monthly / Yes - Weekly**

If yes, cost: €1 - €50 €51 - €200 €201 - €500 Over €500

- **Maintenance cost – included in the subscription? Yes / No / Not applicable**

If no, cost per month: €1 - €50 €51 - €200 €201 - €500 Over €500

- **Maintenance / replacement parts:**

Easy to obtain Difficult to obtain Not obtainable Don't know

- **Technical / mechanical support provided on farm, after purchase? Yes / No**

Training requirements

- **Training required to install / use? Yes / No**

If yes, time range? Up to an hour Half day Full day More

- **Additional technical advice required (e.g. advisor time)? Yes / No**

- **Are there additional costs associated with training and/or technical advice? Yes / No**

Benefits (tick all that apply)

Management

- Labour / time saving.
- Accuracy of records (health, management, movements etc.).
- Management decisions for animal groupings.
- Better individual animal management.
- Improved medicine use.
- Better nutrition / meeting requirements better.
- Improved use of feed resource (grazing, concentrates, etc.).
- Product quality improvements (e.g. hay, carcass, growth, milk, etc.).
- Increased information on production system.
- Opportunity for sharing / moving device (more than one location).

Animal

- Reduced stress to the animal(s).
- Improved welfare of the animals(s).
- Additional information on animal behaviour.
- Information on water intake / water availability.
- Information on food intake / food availability.

Technical

- Compatibility with other devices.
- Ease of data transfer to other software.
- Easy to use once installed.

Other

- Reduced stress to farmer / staff.
- Environmental benefits (e.g. reduced wastage, improved biodiversity, etc.)
- Helps to attract new entrants into the small ruminant industries.

Another benefit not listed? Please give details:

Overall summary:

- **Ease of use?** *Scale 1 (Complicated) – 10 (Simple)*
1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

- **Value for money (for this type of benchmark farm)?** Yes / No / Maybe

- **Recommend this tool/technology for use on other types of farm?**
Yes / No / Maybe

- **Additional comments?**

Cost/Benefit analysis

Tool / Technology: **NoFence collars**

Analysis prepared by (country): **Norway**

Production type the tool/technology is relevant for: Dairy / Meat / **Both**

Description of the “benchmark” farm for which the analysis is performed:

Country: Norway

Production type:

Mainly outdoors / Housed 0-3 months a year / **Housed 4-8 months a year** / Mainly indoors

Farm grazing area: 120 ha (10 ha arable land and fenced pasture. Abundant rangeland grazing area for summer grazing.)

Species: **Sheep** / Goat

Number of animals: 30 ewes

Breed: Grey Trønder sheep breed

Number of staff: 1

Costs

Initial set-up

- **Capital costs (Large items e.g. a weigh crate, auto-drafter, etc.):**

€1 - €500 €501- €1,000 €1,001-€2,500 €2,501-€5,000 €5,001-€15,000 > €15,000

- **Individual costs (Smaller items e.g. per tag, per sample, per collar):**

€1 - €20 €21- €50 €51-€200 €201-€500 > €500

- **Equipment leasing costs (if not purchased):**

Annual Monthly Weekly €1 - €50 €51-€200 €201-€500 > €500

- **Lifetime of the technology (approximately how long will it last before needing replaced)?**

1 – 4 weeks 1-6 months 6 – 12 months 1-2 years 2-6 years > 5 years

- **Farm infrastructure requirements:** Decrease Increase No change

- **Percentage of animals within the flock/herd that use/are equipped/take advantage of the technology? 100 %**

Running costs

- **Power source requirements (tick all that apply):**

Not required Mains Battery Solar Other

- **Subscription fee – Needed? Yes / No**

- **If yes**

Per flock / herd <input type="checkbox"/>	Per individual animal <input type="checkbox"/>	Per unit <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Annual <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Monthly <input type="checkbox"/>	Weekly <input type="checkbox"/>
€1 - €50 <input type="checkbox"/>	€51 - €200 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	€201 - €500 <input type="checkbox"/> Over €500 <input type="checkbox"/>

- **Additional licences or permits required? No / Yes – Annual / Yes – Monthly / Yes - Weekly**

If yes, cost: €1 - €50 €51 - €200 €201 - €500 Over €500

- **Maintenance cost – included in the subscription? Yes / No / Not applicable**

If no, cost per month: €1 - €50 €51 - €200 €201 - €500 Over €500

- **Maintenance / replacement parts:**

Easy to obtain Difficult to obtain Not obtainable Don't know

- **Technical / mechanical support provided on farm, after purchase? Yes / No**

Training requirements

- **Training required to install / use? Yes No**

If yes, time range? Up to an hour Half day Full day More

- **Additional technical advice required (e.g. advisor time)? Yes / No**

- **Are there additional costs associated with training and/or technical advice? Yes No**

Benefits (tick all that apply)

Management

- Labour / time saving.
- Accuracy of records (health, management, movements etc.).
- Management decisions for animal groupings.
- Better individual animal management.
- Improved medicine use.
- Better nutrition / meeting requirements better.
- Improved use of feed resource (grazing, concentrates, etc.).
- Product quality improvements (e.g. hay, carcass, growth, milk, etc.).
- Increased information on production system.
- Opportunity for sharing / moving device (more than one location).

Animal

- Reduced stress to the animal(s).
- Improved welfare of the animals(s).
- Additional information on animal behaviour.
- Information on water intake / water availability.
- Information on food intake / food availability.

Technical

- Compatibility with other devices.
- Ease of data transfer to other software.
- Easy to use once installed.

Other

- Reduced stress to farmer / staff.
- Environmental benefits (e.g. reduced wastage, improved biodiversity, etc.)
- Helps to attract new entrants into the small ruminant industries.

Another benefit not listed? Please give details:

Can expand farm grazing area/feed resources available, as there is no need for a physical fence.
May be the tool that will keep sheep farmers into sheep farming, as well as allowing recruitment of young farmers.

Overall summary:

- **Ease of use?** *Scale 1 (Complicated) – 10 (Simple)*

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 **9** 10

- **Value for money (for this type of benchmark farm)?** **Yes / ~~No~~ / ~~Maybe~~**

- **Recommend this tool/technology for use on other types of farm?**

~~Yes~~ / ~~No~~ / Maybe

- **Additional comments?**

Annual costs vary depending on subscription choice. If the system is in use all year there is a fixed price per collar. Payment can also be per collar per day.

Sm@ll Ruminant Technologies

Cost/Benefit analysis

Tool / Technology: **GPS collar (e.g. Telespor or FindMy)**

Analysis prepared by (country): **Norway**

Production type the tool/technology is relevant for: Dairy / **Meat** / Both

Description of the “benchmark” farm for which the analysis is performed:

Country: Norway

Production type:

Mainly outdoors / Housed 0-3 months a year / **Housed 4-8 months a year** / Mainly indoors

Farm grazing area: 120 ha (10 ha arable land and fenced pasture. Abundant rangeland grazing area for summer grazing.)

Species: **Sheep** / Goat

Number of animals: 80 ewes

Breed: Norwegian white sheep

Number of staff: 1

Costs

Initial set-up

- **Capital costs (Large items e.g. a weigh crate, auto-drafter, etc.):**

€1 - €500 €501- €1,000 €1,001-€2,500 €2,501-€5,000 €5,001-€15,000 > €15,000

- **Individual costs (Smaller items e.g. per tag, per sample, per collar):**

€1 - €20 €21- €50 €51-€200 €201-€500 > €500

- **Equipment leasing costs (if not purchased):**

Annual Monthly Weekly €1 - €50 €51-€200 €201-€500 > €500

- **Lifetime of the technology (approximately how long will it last before needing replaced)?**

1 – 4 weeks 1-6 months 6 – 12 months 1-2 years 2-7 years > 5 years

- **Farm infrastructure requirements:** Decrease Increase No change

- **Percentage of animals within the flock/herd that use/are equipped/take advantage of the technology? 20-100 %**

Running costs

- **Power source requirements (tick all that apply):**

Not required Mains Battery Solar Other

- **Subscription fee – Needed? Yes / No**

○ If yes

Per flock / herd <input type="checkbox"/>	Per individual animal <input type="checkbox"/>	Per unit <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Annual <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Monthly <input type="checkbox"/>	Weekly <input type="checkbox"/>
€1 - €50 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	€51 - €200 <input type="checkbox"/>	€201 - €500 <input type="checkbox"/>
		Over €500 <input type="checkbox"/>

- **Additional licences or permits required? No / Yes – Annual / Yes – Monthly / Yes - Weekly**

If yes, cost: €1 - €50 €51 - €200 €201 - €500 Over €500

- **Maintenance cost – included in the subscription? Yes No / Not applicable**

If no, cost per month: €1 - €50 €51 - €200 €201 - €500 Over €500

- **Maintenance / replacement parts:**

Easy to obtain Difficult to obtain Not obtainable Don't know

- **Technical / mechanical support provided on farm, after purchase? Yes No /**

Training requirements

- **Training required to install / use? Yes / No**

If yes, time range? Up to an hour Half day Full day More

- **Additional technical advice required (e.g. advisor time)? Yes No /**

- **Are there additional costs associated with training and/or technical advice? Yes No /**

Benefits (tick all that apply)

Management

- Labour / time saving.
- Accuracy of records (health, management, movements etc.).
- Management decisions for animal groupings.
- Better individual animal management.
- Improved medicine use.
- Better nutrition / meeting requirements better.
- Improved use of feed resource (grazing, concentrates, etc.).
- Product quality improvements (e.g. hay, carcass, growth, milk, etc.).
- Increased information on production system.
- Opportunity for sharing / moving device (more than one location).

Animal

- Reduced stress to the animal(s).
- Improved welfare of the animals(s).
- Additional information on animal behaviour.
- Information on water intake / water availability.
- Information on food intake / food availability.

Technical

- Compatibility with other devices.
- Ease of data transfer to other software.
- Easy to use once installed.

Other

- Reduced stress to farmer / staff.
- Environmental benefits (e.g. reduced wastage, improved biodiversity, etc.)
- Helps to attract new entrants into the small ruminant industries.

Another benefit not listed? Please give details:

Surveillance of animals on unfenced rangeland pastures is a concern in the public opinion as well as for sheep farmers. This tech can improve this situation.

Also land use is under pressure, and documenting the land used for grazing animals is important to document land use needs for farming.

Maybe the tool that will keep sheep farmers into sheep farming, as well as allowing recruitment of young farmers.

Overall summary:

- **Ease of use?** *Scale 1 (Complicated) – 10 (Simple)*

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 **9** 10

- **Value for money (for this type of benchmark farm)?** Yes / ~~No~~ / ~~Maybe~~

- **Recommend this tool/technology for use on other types of farm?**

Yes / ~~No~~ / ~~Maybe~~

- **Additional comments?**

Annual costs vary depending on coverage. Collars that need to communicate through satellites are more costly than those that communicate through GSM.

Sm@ll Ruminant Technologies

Cost/Benefit analysis

Tool / Technology: **Drone (quadruple drone)**

Analysis prepared by (country): **Norway**

Production type the tool/technology is relevant for: Dairy / **Meat** / Both

Description of the “benchmark” farm for which the analysis is performed:

Country: Norway

Production type:

Mainly outdoors / Housed 0-3 months a year / **Housed 4-8 months a year** / Mainly indoors

Farm grazing area: 120 ha (10 ha arable land and fenced pasture. Abundant rangeland grazing area for summer grazing.)

Species: **Sheep** / Goat

Number of animals: 80 ewes

Breed: Norwegian white sheep

Number of staff: 1

Costs

Initial set-up

- **Capital costs (Large items e.g. a weigh crate, auto-drafter, etc.):**

€1 - €500 €501- €1,000 €1,001-€2,500 €2,501-€5,000 €5,001-€15,000 > €15,000

- **Individual costs (Smaller items e.g. per tag, per sample, per collar):**

€1 - €20 €21- €50 €51-€200 €201-€500 > €500

- **Equipment leasing costs (if not purchased):**

Annual Monthly Weekly €1 - €50 €51-€200 €201-€500 > €500

- **Lifetime of the technology (approximately how long will it last before needing replaced)?**

1 – 4 weeks 1-6 months 6 – 12 months 1-2 years 2-8 years > 5 years

- **Farm infrastructure requirements:** Decrease Increase No change

- **Percentage of animals within the flock/herd that use/are equipped/take advantage of the technology? _____%**

Running costs

- **Power source requirements (tick all that apply):**

Not required Mains Battery Solar Other

- **Subscription fee – Needed? Yes / No**

○ If yes

Per flock / herd <input type="checkbox"/>	Per individual animal <input type="checkbox"/>	Per unit <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Annual <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Monthly <input type="checkbox"/>	Weekly <input type="checkbox"/>
€1 - €50 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	€51 - €200 <input type="checkbox"/>	€201 - €500 <input type="checkbox"/>
		Over €500 <input type="checkbox"/>

- **Additional licences or permits required? No** Yes – Annual / Yes – Monthly / Yes - Weekly

If yes, cost: €1 - €50 €51 - €200 €201 - €500 Over €500

- **Maintenance cost – included in the subscription? Yes / No** Not applicable

If no, cost per month: €1 - €50 €51 - €200 €201 - €500 Over €500

- **Maintenance / replacement parts:**

Easy to obtain Difficult to obtain Not obtainable Don't know

- **Technical / mechanical support provided on farm, after purchase? Yes / No**

Training requirements

- **Training required to install / use? Yes** No

If yes, time range? Up to an hour Half day Full day More

- **Additional technical advice required (e.g. advisor time)? Yes / No**

- **Are there additional costs associated with training and/or technical advice? Yes / No**

Benefits (tick all that apply)

Management

- Labour / time saving.
- Accuracy of records (health, management, movements etc.).
- Management decisions for animal groupings.
- Better individual animal management.
- Improved medicine use.
- Better nutrition / meeting requirements better.
- Improved use of feed resource (grazing, concentrates, etc.).
- Product quality improvements (e.g. hay, carcass, growth, milk, etc.).
- Increased information on production system.
- Opportunity for sharing / moving device (more than one location).

Animal

- Reduced stress to the animal(s).
- Improved welfare of the animals(s).
- Additional information on animal behaviour.
- Information on water intake / water availability.
- Information on food intake / food availability.

Technical

- Compatibility with other devices.
- Ease of data transfer to other software.
- Easy to use once installed.

Other

- Reduced stress to farmer / staff.
- Environmental benefits (e.g. reduced wastage, improved biodiversity, etc.)
- Helps to attract new entrants into the small ruminant industries.

Another benefit not listed? Please give details:

Surveillance of animals on unfenced rangeland pastures is a concern and the gathering of sheep from these areas before winter is time consuming. In addition to saving work hours, as the drone can search a larger area, also health and safety can be improved. Using the drone to move sheep from steep hills and rocky landscape is a health and safety issue for people.

Maybe the tool that will keep sheep farmers into sheep farming, as well as allowing recruitment of young farmers.

Overall summary:

- **Ease of use?** *Scale 1 (Complicated) – 10 (Simple)*

1 2 3 4 **5** 6 7 8 9 10

- **Value for money (for this type of benchmark farm)?** **Yes / ~~No~~ / ~~Maybe~~**

- **Recommend this tool/technology for use on other types of farm?**

Yes / ~~No~~ / ~~Maybe~~

- **Additional comments?**

The use of the drone can be restricted by weather conditions.

Horizon 2020
Programme

Sm@ll Ruminant Technologies

Cost/Benefit Analysis

Tool / Technology: **Feed ration planner**

Analysis prepared by (country): **UK**

Production type the tool/technology is relevant for: Dairy / Meat / **Both**

Description of the “benchmark” farm for which the analysis is performed:

Country: UK

Production type:

Mainly outdoors / Housed 0-3 months a year / Housed 4-8 months a year / Mainly indoors

Farm grazing area: ~1,000 ha

Species: **Sheep** / Goat

Number of animals: 700 ewes

Breed: Predominantly Scottish Blackface

Number of staff: 2

Costs

Initial set-up

- **Capital costs (Large items e.g. a weigh crate, auto-drafter, etc.):**

€1 - €500 €501- €1,000 €1,001-€2,500 €2,501-€5,000 €5,001-€15,000 > €15,000

- **Individual costs (Smaller items e.g. per tag, per sample, per collar):**

€1 - €20 €21- €50 €51-€200 €201-€500 > €500

- **Equipment leasing costs (if not purchased):**

Annual Monthly Weekly €1 - €50 €51-€200 €201-€500 > €500

- **Lifetime of the technology (approximately how long will it last before needing replaced)?**

1 – 4 weeks 1-6 months 6 – 12 months 1-2 years 2-9 years > 5 years

- **Farm infrastructure requirements:** Decrease Increase No change

- **Percentage of animals within the flock/herd that use/are equipped/take advantage of the technology? 100 %**

Running costs

- **Power source requirements (tick all that apply):**

Not required Mains Battery Solar Other

- **Subscription fee – Needed? Yes / **No****

○ If yes

Per flock / herd <input type="checkbox"/>	Per individual animal <input type="checkbox"/>	Per unit <input type="checkbox"/>
Annual <input type="checkbox"/>	Monthly <input type="checkbox"/>	Weekly <input type="checkbox"/>
€1 - €50 <input type="checkbox"/>	€51 - €200 <input type="checkbox"/>	€201 - €500 <input type="checkbox"/>
		Over €500 <input type="checkbox"/>

- **Additional licences or permits required? **No** Yes – Annual / Yes – Monthly / Yes - Weekly**

If yes, cost: €1 - €50 €51 - €200 €201 - €500 Over €500

- **Maintenance cost – included in the subscription? Yes / **No** / Not applicable**

If no, cost per month: €1 - €50 €51 - €200 €201 - €500 Over €500

- **Maintenance / replacement parts:**

Easy to obtain Difficult to obtain Not obtainable Don't know

- **Technical / mechanical support provided on farm, after purchase? Yes / **No****

Training requirements

- **Training required to install / use? **Yes** / No**

If yes, time range? Up to an hour Half day Full day More

- **Additional technical advice required (e.g. advisor time)? Yes / **No****

- **Are there additional costs associated with training and/or technical advice? Yes / **No****

Benefits (tick all that apply)

Management

- Labour / time saving.
- Accuracy of records (health, management, movements etc.).
- Management decisions for animal groupings.
- Better individual animal management.
- Improved medicine use.
- Better nutrition / meeting requirements better.
- Improved use of feed resource (grazing, concentrates, etc.).
- Product quality improvements (e.g. hay, carcass, growth, milk, etc.).
- Increased information on production system.
- Opportunity for sharing / moving device (more than one location).

Animal

- Reduced stress to the animal(s).
- Improved welfare of the animals(s).
- Additional information on animal behaviour.
- Information on water intake / water availability.
- Information on food intake / food availability.

Technical

- Compatibility with other devices.
- Ease of data transfer to other software.
- Easy to use once installed.

Other

- Reduced stress to farmer / staff .
- Environmental benefits (e.g. reduced wastage, improved biodiversity, etc.)
- Helps to attract new entrants in to the small ruminant industries.

Another benefit not listed? Please give details:

The tool is free to download from the AHDB webpage.

Data helps to plan when additional supplementation is required.

Overall summary:

- **Ease of use?** *Scale 1 (Complicated) – 10 (Simple)*

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 **9** 10

- **Value for money (for this type of benchmark farm)?** Yes / ~~No~~ / ~~Maybe~~

- **Recommend this tool/technology for use on other types of farm?**

Yes / ~~No~~ / ~~Maybe~~

- **Additional comments?**

The tool is free but requires regular measurements using a plate meter/sward stick to collect pasture data and a computer.

Mainly useful for improved and/or semi-improved grazing. Might not be so practical for extensive hill ground grazing.

Data collected can be used with some mobile phone apps and farm management software (some of these may involve a subscription fee).

More sophisticated ration software are available, which come at a cost, but allow more detailed rations to be set for various different classes of animal (pregnant ewes, finishing lambs, etc.).

e.g. **DietCheck for Sheep** - <https://dietcheck.co.uk/software/dietcheck-for-sheep>.
 Small Ruminant Nutrition System - ([Model: SRNS \(nutritionmodels.com\)](http://Model:SRNS(nutritionmodels.com)))

